

FAITH INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY AND SEMINARY

EQUIPPING AFRICAN AMERICAN PASTORS TO UTILIZE
MENTAL HEALTH SKILLSETS IN THEIR CHURCHES

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EQUIPPING AFRICAN AMERICAN PASTORS TO UTILIZE
MENTAL HEALTH SKILLSETS IN THEIR CHURCHES

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CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vvii
ABSTRACT	ix
Chapter	Page
1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. PRESENTATION OF PROBLEM AND PURPOSE STATEMENT	4
Problem.....	4
Purpose	8
3. THEOLOGICAL RATIONALE	9
God Created the Sabbath for Humans to Have Needed Rest	9
God Has Given Christians a Spirit of Strength and Power.....	16
God Provided a Means for Humans to Have Balance and Self-care	24
4. THEORETICAL PRESUPPOSITION	31
The African American Experience Develops Personal Resiliency.....	31
Mental Health Involves Understanding Intersectionality	36
Mental Health Skillsets Aid Teaching, Learning, and Healing.....	46
5. PROJECT PLANS AND OBJECTIVES	56
Participants' Objectives	56
Personal Objectives for the Project	57
6. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROJECT.....	59
7. ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF PROJECT DATA.....	70

Evaluation and Assessment Tools.....	70
Analysis and Evaluation of Participants' Data.....	72
Analysis and Evaluation of Personal Data.....	77
Analysis and Evaluation of Project Data.....	84
Conclusion.....	87

Appendix	Page
1. COGNITIVE THEORY.....	89
2. PSYCHODYNAMIC THEORY.....	90
3. BEHAVIORAL THEORY.....	91
4. SELECTION OF THE MENTAL HEALTH SERIES.....	92
5. PARTICIPANT'S PERIODIIOC FEEDBACK FORM.....	94
6. PARTICIPANT'S PERSONAL GOAL FORMS.....	95
7. MODIFIED MENTAL HEALTH KNOWLEDGE INVENTORY.....	96
8. TEACHER/FACILATATOR'S EVALUATION FORM.....	98
9. PARTICIPANT'S PROJECT EVALUATION FORM.....	99
10. PARTICIPANT'S ENROLLMENT AND PERSONAL HISTORY FORM.....	101
11. PROJECT ASSESSMENT INTERVIEW FORM.....	102
12. PERSONAL LESSON PLANS.....	104
SELECTED BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	107
PERSONAL DATA SHEET.....	120

TABLES

Table	Page
1. Analysis of Pretest and Posttest for Mental Health Knowledge Inventory.....	72
2. Group Discussion and Homework Percentages.....	74
3. Reported Teachable Moments.....	75
4. Participants' Skill-Related Intentions.....	77
5. Evaluation of Facilitator.....	83
6. Ministry Change Indicators.....	87

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ABSTRACT

The ministry project facilitator sought to equip African American pastors and church leaders with mental health skillsets. The facilitator conducted six two-hour seminars on the following topics: (1) introduction of the theological rationale and theoretical presuppositions; (2) exploring and understanding mental health; (3) the African American Experience, i.e., trauma and other contributing indicators of mental health concerns; (4) race, gender, and intersectionality; (5) coping skills; and (6) implementing mental health resources. The facilitator led four pastoral support groups to reinforce learned skills. The writer provided a thorough bibliography with appendices. The project analysis demonstrated that with training and resources, pastors became more capable of addressing mental health concerns and capitalizing on teachable moments related to mental health.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

African American churches have traditionally stressed the need to live moral Christian lives. For some, the disconnect has been their refusal to seek mental health skillsets outside of the church. Although well intended, an over-emphasis and over-reliance upon prayer and faith has been often recommended over therapy or counseling.

An area where both pastors and laity have often struggled has been resolving or coming to terms with current and past traumatic events such as grief, divorce, and a host of other emotional maladies that plague every community. Bernard Richardson suggests:

Presently, black people with personal or interpersonal concerns can choose between seeking the services of a clergy person or a mental health professional. They can also decide to seek both services simultaneously. However, whether or not a parishioner seeks the services of a mental health professional may depend largely on the attitudes the minister has toward mental illness and psychological services.¹

There was evidence that various denominations and religious organizations shared this enigma. From the onset of the Middle Passage, African Americans consistently endured racism and their churches or places of worship has been one of the few means of hope.

From the American slave trade, the Jim Crow Era, and the Civil Rights Movement to the present, African American communities experienced various levels of trauma. African American churches have continued to serve as hubs and pillars within their communities but have lagged in meeting their post-traumatic needs.

¹Bernard Richardson, Attitudes of Black Clergy toward Mental Health Professionals: Implications for Pastoral Care, *Journal of Pastoral Care* 43, no. 1 (1989): 33, <https://doi:10.1177/002234098904300105>.

Within African American communities, “taboo” topics such as sexual abuse, domestic violence, or something as simple as depression have seldom been discussed. As a result, those needing help have rarely sought help outside their local churches. When I proposed the idea of implementing a program to integrate mental health skillsets for pastors and their church members, the pastors were elated.

An area where African American pastors have often struggled has been communicating the need for their congregants to seek assistance from mental health experts when needed. This stemmed from a lack of formal training and/or resources.

Trinna L. Copeland’s dissertation, *African American Senior Pastor’s Beliefs about Mental Health Treatment* asserts:

Fulfilling the role of spiritual advisor and counselor could be a challenge for clergy if they have not received training and are limited on resources for addressing serious mental health issues (Allen et al., 2010). Allen et al. (2010) explained how senior pastors offer scripture and prayer as tools for coping, and the belief in God for healing as tools of assistance for persons seeking guidance in this informal setting. This leads to questions regarding whether the individual seeking aid needs additional tools for coping: Would that individual benefit further from a referral to a mental health agency given the gravity of the issue being presented? If African Americans do participate in treatment, is it important for senior pastors and mental health clinicians to understand what participants need to begin and continue in treatment?²

Copeland’s assertions conveyed the need for informed spiritual advisors within their churches. She also presented rhetorical yet logical questions regarding what pastors and mental health experts should consider. The challenge for pastors and members has been not to view seeking mental health during moments of crisis or therapy for trauma as a lack of faith in God.

² Trinna Copeland, “African American Senior Pastor’s Belief about Mental Health Treatment” (2019), <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=7470&context=dissertations>.

The Bible has often addressed faith, prayer, and perseverance. As mentioned earlier, all of those are essential qualities in living a wholesome Christian life. Since many pastors and theologians have approached psychology and how man processes emotions as a science, in many ministries, a chasm existed between it and theology.

Each of the pastors who participated in this research learned more about mental health better to equip themselves and their members with mental health coping skills and resources. When I suggested this idea to them, they eagerly embraced the concept and believe it has enhanced their lives and their members.

CHAPTER 2

PRESENTATION OF PROBLEM AND PURPOSE STATEMENT

Problem

I recently audited a group of three African American pastors regarding mental health skillsets. Only one pastor had received formal mental health skillset training in this group of three. None of the pastors had taught or tried to integrate mental health skillsets within their congregations.

Mental health tended to be seldom discussed and had been often intentionally dismissed in African American churches. Many pastors do not know how to integrate or convey mental health within their ministries. Historically, the perception of African Americans considered mentally unstable or deficient were viewed with disdain. In the book *The Unapologetic Guide to Mental Health*, Rheedra Walker, PhD, states:

In a research study that was conducted in the early '90s, church pastors were asked their opinions about Black suicide. They responded by saying that suicide was a 'denial of Black identity and culture.' To them, being Black is about struggle—there are no easy answers or easy outs. The overarching message from the pastors was that suicide is 'a white thing' and that Black people are resilient because of the history of struggle and making a way despite being left out of mainstream society politically, economically, and socially.³

Instead of mental health, therapy, or counseling outside of the church, many pastors stressed faith in God alone. Because of this position, victims of suicide were often viewed as people who lack faith and missed the mark. This pastoral position has also sent subliminal messages to other church members. Suicide has easily been regarded as the final yet fatal cry for help. In many instances, before suicide, depression has often been

³ Rheedra Walker, *The Unapologetic Guide to Black Mental Health: Navigate an Unequal System, Learn Tools for Emotional Wellness, and Get the Help You Deserve* (Oakland, Ca: New Harbinger Publications, Inc, 2020).

seen as a chief indicator. *The Journal of Pastoral Theology* asserted, “There are, within the African American community, subliminal risks associated with acknowledging that one suffers from depression. The consequences are experienced personally, socially, financially, and spiritually.”⁴

While considering the previously stated position, Dr. Bernard Richardson maintained:

Reports on research in which 27 pastors and 81 parishioners in a Michigan city responded to a Semantic Differential instrument in an attempt to measure attitudes of black clergy toward mental health professionals. Statistical analyses suggest that black clergy tend to hold favorable attitudes toward mental health workers, a propensity running counter to some popular notions. Postulates a variety of possible reasons for the finding and urges additional research to guide cooperative efforts of black clergy and mental health professionals in their common desire to foster the social, spiritual, and psychological well-being of persons in the black community.⁵

Mental health has become a multi-layered problem for many African Americans. Systemic racism, cultural biases, and stereotypes are just a few hurdles that have appeared insurmountable when seeking professional health care. Depression, Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), eating disorders, and learning to cope within marginalized societies has been the norm for many African Americans. Unaddressed, these somewhat inherent obstacles have had a detrimental impact on many people, their families, communities, and their trajectories in life.

The critical component for African American communities and churches has been the black family. Because many families have been severely bruised or broken, it has also

⁴ Wynnetta Wimberley, “The Culture of Stigma Surrounding Depression in the African American Family and Community,” *Journal of Pastoral Theology* 25, no. 1 (March 2015): 18, <https://doi.org/10.1179/1064986715z.0000000004>.

⁵ Bernard Richardson, “Attitudes of Black Clergy toward Mental Health Professionals: Implications for Pastoral Care,” *Journal of Pastoral Care* 43, no. 1 (March 1989): 33, <https://doi.org/10.1177/002234098904300105>.

been evident within society, in their relationships with others, and in how they have viewed God. Because the traditional Biblical concept of home was dismantled at the onset of slavery, the reinstitution of their families have remained an arduous task. All of those, as mentioned earlier, can be encapsulated into two words: cultural trauma.

According to Ron Eyerman, “The ‘trauma’ in question is slavery, not as an institution or even experience, but as collective memory, a form of remembrance that grounded the identity-formation of a people. There is a difference between trauma as it affects individuals and as a cultural process.”⁶

The system of inherent slavery and white superiority in America, at its very core, has been intertwined and has created a thwarted view of Christianity. Evidence has been found in countless historical documents, such as Manifest Destiny, the U.S. Constitution, and the Bill of Rights, before any ratifications or amendments were ever made. This disenfranchised introduction of Christianity, being a caste system, was held by most enslaved African Americans and propagated by most Whites.

World-renown theologian, pastor, and author John MacArthur asserts:

To fully understand the New Testament’s use of slave language, we need to begin with a historical perspective regarding the practice of slavery in the Greco-Roman era. Slavery was a pervasive social structure in the first-century Roman Empire. In fact, it was so commonplace that its existence as an institution was never seriously questioned by anyone. Slaves of all ages, genders, and ethnicities constituted an important socioeconomic class in ancient Rome. Roughly one-fifth of the empire’s population were slaves—totaling as many as twelve million at the outset of the first century AD.⁷

⁶ Ron Eyerman, *Cultural Trauma: Slavery and the Formation of African American Identity* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001), 1.

⁷ John MacArthur, *Slave: The Hidden Truth about Your Identity in Christ* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson), chap. 2, iBooks.

This robust view of the Greco-Roman slavery system was used as a blueprint to later substantiate and proselytize slavery in the West. Unlike the Roman Empire, the Others were exclusively of African or Native American descent. The humanity or humanness of enslaved people was debatable, and, in many instances, they were regarded as mere property, chattel, or beasts of the field. Since the abolition of slavery, the descendants of that system have relied on their churches for solace and answers far more than any other institution. From slavery, Jim Crow, and the Civil Rights era to the present, pastors and churches have been the bedrock for answers during troubled times.

During the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Faduma Orishatukeh asserted:

The tendency in the Negro Church is to look for “these manifestations rather than to work for the indwelling spirit who is the cause of such manifestations. Parallel with this tendency in the church, is the effort which is being made after expression of religious life when it should be directed along the line of impressing it. The church is in need of a deep spiritual life, nevertheless it is impossible to express what is not previously impressed in the mind.⁸

Another area of great concern for African Americans has been the perception of a lack of integrity between doctors and patients. Many African Americans have been distrustful of doctors when conveying their symptoms and have left feeling unheard, dismissed, or disregarded. From slavery until the present, reluctance and skepticism has still lingered.

Hence, for many African American churchgoers the challenge and potential remedy has remained within the chasm between Christianity and psychology. Since many pastors and leaders in predominately African American churches have shied away from

⁸ Faduma Orishatukeh, *The Defects of the Negro Church: The American Negro Academy. Occasional Papers No. 10*, (Hardpress Publishing, 2016), chap. 1, iBooks.

therapy and psychology, for some, unless some psychological principles are embraced, total holistic healing may be a fruitless endeavor.

In his book *Strategic Pastoral Counseling*, psychologist David Benner, PhD, asserted:

Attempting to find its identity within this therapeutic culture, pastoral counseling has often experienced tension between the pastoral and the psychological. Some forms of pastoral counseling have borne more resemblance to modern psychotherapy than to historic Christian soul care. Other pastors have sought to distance themselves entirely from psychological counseling, seeking simply to offer biblically based spiritual counsel.⁹

The distance that Benner identified has become one of the main obstacle that must be surmounted. In order for this to be achieved a more thorough understanding of scripture and a pragmatic approach to counseling has become crucial.

Purpose

The purpose of this project is to equip a selected group of African American pastors within the states of Tennessee and Georgia to utilize mental health skillsets in their churches.

⁹ David Benner, *Strategic Pastoral Counseling: A Short-Term Structured Model*, (Baker Book House Company, 2003), chap. 1, iBooks.

CHAPTER THREE

THEOLOGICAL RATIONALE

God Created the Sabbath for Humans to Have Needed Rest

God created the world in six days, and on the seventh day, He rested. God's creation did not deplete His strength, but He set a precedence for mankind to follow. As humans, the Sabbath was set to prioritize allotting time to reflect upon Him and recalibrate by resting. God used this divine mandate for man to rest to expose man's vulnerability without it.

A basic understanding of the Old Testament and Jewish history must be understood fully to grasp God's intent for creating the Sabbath and given insight into the original intent for it to be holy.

Cristian Vaida contended:

The Sabbath is part of Jewish tradition. In Christianity, it has taken on a new meaning. Both faiths saw it as a gift from God, a tool to affirm one's spiritual creed and identity, and a way to maintain a distinct faith identity. The secularism of contemporary society has resulted in a misinterpretation of the purpose of Sunday rest and a disregard for the spiritual aspects that the Sunday celebration involves. A false perception of Sunday rest has emerged in modern times: It is not perceived as a divine gift that enables a spiritual ministry, which leads to resistance and opposition to the restless anxiety of the consumerist world and serves as an alternative to advertising's demanding presence in this world.¹⁰

Although the idea of rest may seem foreign or antiquated idea today, its principles made rest mandatory for Judaism and the early church. Although Sabbath-keeping has been and remains a debatable topic for most Christians, evidence of its practice existed in the Church during her infancy.

¹⁰ Cristian Vaida, "Sabbath and Sunday: The Meaning of the Day of Rest in the Ancient Church – a Hope for the Future?," *Hervormde Teologiese Studies* 79, no. 1 (February 28, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v79i1.8263>.

Vaida provided evidence of this with Tertullian's written account:

In Tertullian's work *De oratione*, we find a passage that is often cited as evidence of Christian Sunday rest in the pre-Constantinian period: But we must guard ourselves ... on the day of the Lord's resurrection not only from this exercise (i.e. kneeling in prayer), but from every attitude and exercise of fear, and also defer business [*differeiltis etiam negotia*], so as not to give the devil any place [*ne quem diabolo locum demus*] (eds. Reifferscheid & Wissowa 1890:196).¹¹

Luisa J. Gallagher's *A Theology of Rest: Sabbath Principles for Ministry*

suggested:

Christian educators must train pastors and lay ministers to embrace the practice of Sabbath rest with the same rigor that they adopt to prepare for the specific tasks and functions of ministry. It is by encountering God in Sabbath rest that ministers and believers alike are able to gain a balanced perspective on life and ministry. Adopting a Sabbath rhythm enables ministers to pursue a right relationship with God and others and assists individuals in reaching holistic health and longevity in ministry.¹²

For society to function better, the idea of rest must extend beyond one person or family to society as a whole. The mental well-being of a person, city, or state is attached to the understanding and ability to set time aside for proper and consistent rest. When there is a lack of rest, a person's ability to focus decreases, and there is an increase in irritability, potentially leading to serious health issues.

Because of humanity's innate need to relax, rest, and recalibrate, God has set this precedence not only for Himself in Genesis 2:2-3 but also for the entire nation Israel in Exodus. A pivotal passage of scripture that supported this was found in Exodus 20:8-11:

Remember the sabbath day, to keep it holy. Six days shalt thou labour, and do all thy work: But the seventh day is the sabbath of the LORD thy God: in it thou shalt

¹¹ Cristian Vaida, "Sabbath and Sunday: The Meaning of the Day of Rest in the Ancient Church – a Hope for the Future?," *Hervormde Teologiese Studies* 79, no. 1 (February 28, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v79i1.8263>

¹² Luisa J. Gallagher, "A Theology of Rest: Sabbath Principles for Ministry," *Christian Education Journal: Research on Educational Ministry* 16, no. 1 (February 20, 2019): 134, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739891318821124>.

not do any work, thou, nor thy son, nor thy daughter, thy manservant, nor thy maidservant, nor thy cattle, nor thy stranger that is within thy gates: For in six days the LORD made heaven and earth, the sea, and all that in them is, and rested the seventh day: wherefore the LORD blessed the sabbath day, and hallowed it.¹³

The aforementioned Scripture indicated that God incorporated a period of mandatory rest for His society. Although, most Christians do not observe the Sabbath on Saturdays, the same intended principles should be applied. Because work, family, and church can easily fill a person's plate, and rest has become unscheduled and inconsistent.

Regarding the benefits of Sabbath-like rest for Christians, in the *Christian Education Journal: Research on Educational Ministry*, Luisa J. Gallagher noted:

Christian pastors and lay ministers experience high levels of prolonged stress comparable to employees in other helping professions. Based on MBI surveys from 11,067 participants in helping professions, pastors experience burnout at similar rates to social workers, counselors, and emergency professionals, yet they experience burnout at lower rates than teachers and police officers (Adams et al., 2017, pp. 167-170). Adams and co-authors (2017) state, 'Clergy appear to be doing better than police and emergency personnel. However, clergy burnout is worse than that of counselors. There may be strategies that counselors use, like having backup and on-call support that would benefit clergy' (p. 170). The type of work that ministry professionals engage in is inherently stressful. Without thoughtful strategies and foresight, burnout can impact an individual's health and well-being, and overall quality of life.¹⁴

As the statistics above indicated, pastors and those involved in ministry were not exempt from stress or burnout. The slightest misunderstanding of scripture can potentially lead to habitually overextending oneself. Commonly misused is "I can do all things through Christ which strengtheneth me" (Philippians 4:13). Poor exegesis, such as

¹³ Unless otherwise noted all Scripture quotations are taken from the *Holy Bible*: King James Version published by Hendrickson Publishers, Peabody, 2004.

¹⁴ Luisa J. Gallagher, 2019. "A Theology of Rest: Sabbath Principles for Ministry." *Christian Education Journal Research on Educational Ministry* 16, no. 1: 134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739891318821124>.

this, has easily led some church leaders and members towards this approach regarding ministry.

God incarnate, Jesus, also exemplified His humanity by resting. Several passages recorded Jesus sleeping, observing the Sabbath, and exhibiting emotional intelligence. In the pursuit of Christ-like behavior, rest and recuperation have often been overlooked. In addition, Jesus took numerous occasions to rest during His three years of earthly ministry.

The Sabbath was much more than a day of worship and rest. David Guzik took a fresh perspective on how Christians should view the Sabbath in its totality. In his Biblical commentary, Guzik noted:

ii. Like everything in the Bible, we understand the sabbath of solemn rest from the perspective of the whole Bible, not only this single passage. With this understanding, we see that there is a real sense in which Jesus fulfilled the purpose and the plan of the Sabbath for us and in us (Hebrews 4:9-11). Jesus is our rest. When we remember His finished work, we remember the Sabbath, and we remember the rest.¹⁵

Guzik's observations were not tied to legalism but echoed a pragmatic approach toward the Sabbath and man's need for rest. After God created the world, His decision to rest set a precedence for humankind. Six days of work were expected, but there should also be a consistent time set apart to relax, recuperate, and recalibrate. Because God is God, His creation or creative processes did not tire Him. Man, on the other hand, needed time to avoid burnout and mental instability.

¹⁵ David Guzik, "Study Guide for Leviticus 23 by David Guzik," Blue Letter Bible, accessed November 1, 2023, https://www.blueletterbible.org/comm/guzik_david/study-guide/leviticus/leviticus-23.cfm.

Even when Jesus walked the earth in human form, controversies regarding the Sabbath and its meaning loomed. G. K. Beale's and D. A. Carson's *Commentary on the Old Testament and the Use of the New Testament* asserted:

The controversy over plucking grain on the Sabbath (Matt. 12:1–8) relies heavily on the account of David's behavior at Nob in 1 Sam. 21:1–6. If under special circumstances Ahimelech allowed David and his companions to eat the sacred show-bread despite the restrictions of Lev. 24:5–9 that only priests could eat this food, how much more appropriate it is for Jesus to determine when he and his disciples may pluck grain on a Sabbath (12:3–4).¹⁶

Their point of view shed light on the misconception that the Sabbath was created solely for worship. In some religious circles, including many African American churches, this one-dimensional legalist approach towards the need and divine mandate for rest has lingered. An over-preoccupation with worship was not God's original intent. A proper understanding and exegeses of Scripture is required. Every pastor, minister, and church leader's goal should be to ensure that their members have understood that mental health was a priority set by God.

The *Africa Bible Commentary: A One-Volume Commentary Written by 70 African Scholars* advised:

During his life here on earth, Jesus made it abundantly clear that keeping the letter of the law does not make anyone closer to God. He stated that he is the Lord of the Sabbath (Matt 12:8; Mark 2:28; Luke 6:5) and demonstrated that meeting human needs takes precedence over the Sabbath observance (Matt 12:11-14; John 5:1-9).

In our time, we need to ensure that in observing our day of rest on Sunday, we do not become like the Pharisees and focus on obeying the letter of the law. We should use the day as an opportunity to draw closer to God and to his people. But we must also beware of spending so much time at church that we have no time to rest our bodies. The principle of the Sabbath excludes any attempt to please God simply on the basis of these externals of our behaviour. Its focus is on our

¹⁶ G. K. Beale and D. A. Carson, *Commentary on the Old Testament and the Use of the New Testament* (Grand Rapids: Baker Publishing Group, 2011), chap. 1, iBooks.

relationship with Jesus Christ, the one sent by God to provide rest for our souls (Matt 11:28).¹⁷

What was interesting about the commentator's observation was Christians used this concept of the Sabbath to grow closer to God and each other. From this perspective, the reason God created the Sabbath can be understood from a more pragmatic position. God created the Sabbath for us to serve not only Him but also ourselves and one another.

A part of the servicing for ourselves included our mental health, which can only be achieved through rest. Everyone needs to detach from labor and the expectations of others to minimize anxiety. Although we are told, according to Philippians 4:6, "be anxious for nothing" because we are human and have the pressures of life and responsibilities, anxiety is a by-product of life.

Coupled with mental rest is physical rest. God has allotted this time for His children to rejuvenate and recover from habitual arduous activities. Meeting the demands of a typical work week easily produces stress and can potentially lead to exhaustion. One of the first examples of how God wanted society to take time to rest from physical labor can be found in Exodus.

According to revealed to Moses in Exodus 16:22, "And it came to pass, *that* on the sixth day they gathered twice as much bread, two omers for one *man*: and all the rulers of the congregation came and told Moses."

This precedence alone conveyed the compassion of God for His creation, man. Unlike the other six days, God desired for man to rest on the seventh day by providing more than enough on the day prior. Without physical and mental rest, people lack

¹⁷ Tokunboh Adeyemo, *Africa Bible Commentary: A One-Volume Commentary Written by 70 African Scholars* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2006), chap. 3, iBooks.

balance. Work standalone has never equaled balance. Other things, such as resting, mentally unplugging, connecting with others, and meditating on the goodness of God, are all equally important. Without balance, anyone is subject to mental health issues. Rest should be deemed as a reward from work. God created man to work, and rest is a part of God's compensation for man's labor.

One of the objectives for fully understanding the Sabbath in modern-day churches should not be to tie them to the ruts of legalism or the law, but to ensure they were exposed to the benefits from its principles. God is still involved and greatly concerned with His creation called mankind.

Everything that God has created has required times of replenishment. Jesus exposed Himself to be the Lord of the Sabbath, in other words, the Lord of rest. In the author Mark Buchanan's book, *The Rest of God: Restoring Your Soul, by Restoring Sabbath*, he pointed to the first time there was a Biblical violation of the Sabbath. As Buchanan noted:

It turns out, God gave only broad and general prescriptions for the Sabbath—cease work, mainly—and here and there an oblique clue. The only incident where a real and actual rule is broken is in Numbers 15, and we learn about the rule in the breach, through the breaking of it. A man is caught gathering brushwood on the Sabbath. Those who catch him haul him in to see Moses and Aaron—implying that this is a serious matter, since Moses long ago established that he would handle only the weightiest rulings (see Exod. 18). Moses asks God what is to be done, and God invokes the death penalty (this is likely the proof text Jesus's opponents were thinking of when they sought to stone him).¹⁸

The aforementioned isolated incident, for some, may seem too harsh, for others, a stern reminder to obey the law to its fullest. While considering this, every Christian should acknowledge Christ as being the fulfillment of the law. With that being said, it is

¹⁸ Mark Buchanan, *The Rest of God: Restoring Your Soul by Restoring Sabbath* (Nashville, Tenn.: W Pub. Group, 2006), chap.7, iBooks.

through the Lord of the Sabbath that rest is truly acquired. When people are tormented mentally, physically, or emotionally, relief and rest should be sought through Christ. Rest in Christ is not constricted to a specific days such as Saturdays or Sundays.

There are numerous Biblical examples where Christ offered on-the-spot immediate relief. He offered relief from every malady and disease without hesitation. The sick found rest from their afflictions in Him. Christ has offered to fill every void.

Succinctly, for Christians to be true benefactors of the Sabbath there must be an understanding of the letter and the spirit of the law. The law that was given to the children of Israel can easily be deemed as unkeepable rules, but how does that fit into the everyday life of Christians today?

When the woman was caught in the act of adultery, Jesus was afforded an excellent opportunity to cast judgement upon her. Instead of condemning her, he charged her accusers to assess themselves. To bring clarity, He explained that adultery begins in the heart. Mere lust can condemn a person. Hence, they were all sinners. Jesus seized this opportunity to offer a teachable moment that exposed the spirit of the law (where grace can be found), instead of imposing the death penalty. Considering all that has been said, the objective of the Sabbath should not be to shackle Christians to legalism, rather through understanding the spirit of the law its divine intent should be seen. As man was designed to work, he also was mandated to rest.

God Has Given Christians a Spirit of Strength and Power

As Christians, our human bodies are viewed as temples where the Holy Spirit resides. A maintenance mindset must be achieved because we are not our own and just mere custodians of what God has given us. As with any house, building, or machine,

there should be a routine maintenance schedule emplaced. Without this, the temple will rapidly deteriorate.

Although anxiety is a part of reality within every culture, Christians need to be reminded of God's position. A pivotal passage of scripture that conveys this point was recorded in Philippians. 4:6-9:

Be careful for nothing; but in everything by prayer and supplication with thanksgiving let your requests be made known unto God. And the peace of God, which passeth all understanding, shall keep your hearts and minds through Christ Jesus. Finally, brethren, whatsoever things are true, whatsoever things are honest, whatsoever things are just, whatsoever things are pure, whatsoever things are lovely, whatsoever things are of good report; if there be any virtue, and if there be any praise, think on these things. Those things, which ye have both learned, and received, and heard, and seen in me, do: and the God of peace shall be with you.

The idea of anxiety has always been prevalent within the African American Church. *The Journal of the I.T.C.* asserted:

Choirs and gospel singers also depict the past and present suffering of blacks in the rural and the urban setting. Not only do men and women weep at these concerts, but a good number of them also faint, shout, and cry out 'thank You's' to Jesus for helping them to endure. The singing is a representation of both the accounts of suffering endured personally and collectively; the insults — 'everybody talking 'bout me'; and the scorn are sung about. Besides the endurance of suffering, there is an expression of the aloneness that blacks have endured, overcome, and will overcome.¹⁹

These observations cannot coexist with how Christians are directed to maintain their temples to include a healthy mental state. When the Apostle Paul was addressing the church in Corinth, he aimed to ensure they perceived themselves with a godly mindset. Regarding this, Paul asserted in 1 Corinthians 6:19-20, "What? know ye not that your body is the temple of the Holy Ghost which is in you, which ye have of God, and ye are

¹⁹ Cheryl Gilkes, *Journal of Interdenominational Theological Center* (Atlanta, GA: The ITC Press, 1980), accessed October 13, 2023, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311617913_The_Black_Church_as_a.

not your own? For ye are bought with a price: therefore glorify God in your body, and in your spirit, which are God's." A healthy mindset must be approached from a godly perspective. There is an appropriate time and season for lamenting, but it should never become the premise of a healthy Christian theological view or approach toward God.

Within churches, anxiety is not limited to adults, but it has also had a significant impact on teens and adolescents. The article, *Religiosity, and Spirituality in the Prevention and Management of Depression and Anxiety in Young People: a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis* asserted:

Historically, religion has had a central role in shaping the psychosocial and moral development of young people. For many, adolescence is a key period for exploration of religious and spiritual beliefs as they relate to purpose of life, vocation, and formation of relationships outside the home. The relatively recent lengthening of adolescence due to earlier onset of puberty and delayed role transitions in the 20s, also means a longer period during which young people can develop their religious and spiritual beliefs, potentially resulting in a deeper and more sophisticated understanding. Young people develop a sense of identity during adolescence, with a dynamic exchange between ecological influences and personal agency. Religion can help foster a personal sense of hope, and meaning in life while increasing prosocial, community-oriented attitudes and behaviours during this developmental stage. Furthermore, religious and spiritual beliefs can contribute to positive mental health through mechanisms such as religious morality, religious coping, and social connectedness due to shared beliefs.²⁰

The role of the pastor within African American communities have been unique.

The Journal of Pastoral Care and Counseling's article, *Pastoral Leaders Perceptions of Mental Health and Relational Concerns with faith Based Organizations* asserted:

Lyles (1992) found that African American pastors see themselves as serving the church's mental health needs by preaching, teaching, and counseling. When considering pastoral leaders, it is important to define the term pastor to better understand its meaning. According to Christian scripture, the pastor's appointment comes from God with a goal of equipping the people (Ephesians 4:11–12, KJV) and serving as an example for them (1 Timothy 4:12, KJV).

²⁰ Sudarshan K Aggarwal et al., "Religiosity and Spirituality in the Prevention and Management of Depression and Anxiety in Young People: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," *BMC Psychiatry* 23, no. 1 (October 10, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-05091-2>.

Pastors engage in self-care while also overseeing the people (1 Timothy 5:23, KJV). Pastoral care and pastoral counseling require distinctive qualities and a particular skill set (Nelson et al., 2012). These pastoral skills may include providing spiritual leadership to parishioners, as well as counseling and pastoral care, in conjunction with providing empathy related to issues that impact individuals across the lifespan, such as grief and loss, financial stress, mental health issues, and family issues (Nelson et al., 2012). Pastors often see themselves as ill-equipped to provide specialized counseling, thus making them more comfortable acting as a liaison for mental health professionals and their flock (Nelson et al., 2012).²¹

The aforementioned served as a foundational challenge and prerequisite that all clergy should be prepared to address. Pastoral counseling is one of the first steps. Pastors must embrace the fact that they are not required to know all the answers. Their goal should be to become better equipped through training and resources. The resources many, if not all, of their members will need at some point in their lives consist of therapists, addiction counselors, psychologists, and psychiatrists, only to name a few.

Jamie Aten and Kent Annan, in an article entitled, *Equip and Empower Your*

Church to Respond to Mental Health Issues noted:

A growing number of churchgoers are turning to their church for help with mental health issues. However, many pastors and church leaders feel ill-equipped and unsure about how best to support their members in this area. In addition, recent studies show that approximately 70 percent of church attendees will experience a trauma at some point in their life and more than 30 percent of pastors are at high or medium risk of burnout. Even as leaders serve, they must safeguard their own mental health.²²

²¹ Darren D. Moore, Charles Williams, and Clinton E. Cooper, "Pastoral Leaders Perceptions of Mental Health and Relational Concerns within Faith Based Organizations," *Journal of Pastoral Care & Counseling: Advancing Theory and Professional Practice through Scholarly and Reflective Publications* 76, no. 2 (March 9, 2022): 80, <https://doi.org/10.1177/15423050221081476>.

²² Jamie Aten and Kent Annan, "Equip and Empower Your Church to Respond to Mental Health Issues," The Better Samaritan with Jamie Aten and Kent Annan, October 6, 2022, <https://www.christianitytoday.com/better-samaritan/2022/october/equip-and-empower-your-church-to-respond-to-mental-health-i.html>.

According to the article, *The Buffering Effect of Social Support on the Relationship between Discrimination and Psychological Distress Among Church-Going African American Adults*, Behavior Research and Therapy reported:

Younger African Americans are likely to perceive the most discrimination, with older groups perceiving less discrimination (Albert et al., 2008; Kessler et al., 1999; D. C.; Watkins, Hudson, Howard Caldwell, Siefert, & Jackson, 2010). Furthermore, incidences of discrimination against African Americans occur at all socioeconomic status levels (RWJF, 2017). In fact, research has demonstrated that African Americans who are higher income earners report experiencing the most discrimination (Albert et al., 2008; Borrell et al., 2007).²³

For church members to operate with a sense of strength and power, pastors should seek to encourage mental health awareness. History has proven African Americans to be resilient people, but is it resiliency because of, or despite having mental health skillsets? Many would say the latter.

Dr. Henry Louis Gates contended,

The signal aspects of African American culture were planted, watered, given light, and nurtured in the Black Church, out of the reach and away from the watchful eyes of those who would choke the life out of it. We have to give the church its due as a source of our ancestors' unfathomable resiliency and perhaps the first formalized site for the collective fashioning and development of so many African American aesthetic forms.²⁴

Because of its history, African American church leaders must continue to evolve, including mental health skillsets, in order to meet the psychological needs of the church. Attesting to the resiliency of many African American churches, Shaonta E. Allen stated:

Public discourses assessing and critiquing the Black Church have led some to perceive it is a dead, or at least dying, institution. In comparing descriptions of

²³ Mai-Ly N. Steers et al., "The Buffering Effect of Social Support on the Relationship between Discrimination and Psychological Distress among Church-Going African-American Adults," *Behaviour Research and Therapy* 115 (April 1, 2019): 121, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2018.10.008>.

²⁴ Henry Louis Gates Jr., "The History and Importance of the Black Church," *Harvard Gazette*, March 9, 2021, <https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2021/03/the-history-and-importance-of-the-black-church/>.

Black churches historically to perceptions of Black churches today, this study has found variations in and across the diverse functions offered by Black religious institutions which ultimately serves as evidence of vitality. Through this vitality, I identify the concept of religious resilience. Religious resilience refers to a religious artifact's capacity to withstand changes in the social, political, and racial landscape that would otherwise undermine its value, yet instead the artifact maintains its perception as a significant component of society that fundamentally influences the lives of individuals and groups.²⁵

One of the greatest struggles for many African Americans (Christians and non-Christians) lies with reconciling the traumatic remanences from the African American experience with the modern-day church. For many, this has caused a disconnect. The entire institution of slavery was created and substantiated by an eisegetical interpretation of Scripture. Johannes Van Oort's asserted:

In *Against Faustus*, the story of Noah and his sons is mainly explained as being Christological: Ham figures as a type of the unbelieving Jews who consented to the murder of Christ, but he is also a type of the Jews because he is 'the slave of his brothers' carrying the books by which the Christians may be instructed. Later Augustine corrects his confusion of Ham with the slave Canaan. The story of Ham (and Canaan) is most extensively discussed in the *City of God*. Neither here nor in the *Expositions on the Psalms*, Ham is described as being black or a slave. The same goes for a number of his other writings. In Augustine's late works *Against Julian* and *Unfinished Work against Julian*, he thoroughly goes into the question of why (although Ham sinned) 'vengeance was brought upon Canaan'. Augustine perceives God's prophecy: from Canaan stems the cursed seed [semen maledictum] of the Canaanites. Nowhere, however, he claims that Ham or his descendants would have been cursed to be black or that all of his offspring were condemned to slavery.²⁶

Although there are some professing Christians who still believe the traditional interpretation, it has had a significant impact on how African Americans see themselves and how many people in the world view them through the lens of religion.

²⁵ Shaonta Allen, "Is the Black Church Dead?: Religious Resilience and the Contemporary Functions of Black Christianity.," *Religions* 14, no. 4 (March 1, 2023): NA, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14040460>.

²⁶ Johannes van Oort, "Black and Slave? 'Mestizo' Augustine on Ham," *Theological Studies/Teologiese Studies* 79, no. 1 (September 20, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v79i1.8689>.

The reality of pastoral burnout is another liability that all church leaders must consider. For example, God called the prophet Moses to lead the Israelites out of Egypt, but he also needed help from others. Eventually, he ordained priests and delegated leaders for each tribe. Pastors cannot be all things to all people; if so, burnout becomes inevitable. Clergy Burnout: A Comparative Study with Other Helping Professions noted:

Clergy attempt to create a shared vision for the congregation and lead the staff and congregants, most of whom work on a volunteer basis, to enact that vision. In the process, clergy negotiate conflict between congregants and take a leadership role in decision-making, such as how to spend limited funds or what positions to take on community issues. These decisions often lack clear right or wrong answers and make clergy vulnerable to criticism. In addition, clergy often have spouses and children who are closely observed by congregants, and for whom congregants may have high or even unrealistic expectations (Lee & Iverson-Gilbert 2003; Morris & Blanton 1994). Lee and Iverson-Gilbert (2003) have proposed four essential ministry stressors for clergy and their families: (a) personal criticism, (b) boundary ambiguity, (c) presumptive expectations, and (d) family criticism. Overall, the stressors that clergy experience are interpersonal in nature as clergy serve a unique role within a social ecology (Proeschold-Bell et al. 2011).²⁷

These issues have become a day-to-day problem within every ministry, but may be more frequent within minority-based ministries. According to the article, *Secondary Traumatic Stress, Religious Coping, and Medical Mistrust among African American Clergy and Religious Leaders*:

Another study that examined 99 Black pastors discovered that 40% of the pastors encountered severely mentally ill congregant members. Additionally, two-thirds of the pastors reported counseling congregants with suicidal proclivities, with ten percent of these involvements being linked to a crisis (Payne 2014). Moreover, religious leaders are often called upon as a means for care and support for those who have faced or are currently facing the trauma of intimate partner violence and

²⁷ Christopher J. Adams et al., "Clergy Burnout: A Comparison Study with Other Helping Professions," *Pastoral Psychology* 66, no. 2 (July 21, 2016): 147, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11089-016-0722-4>.

abuse as well as sexual abuse (Davis and Johnson 2020; Rudolfsson and Tidefors 2009; St. Vil et al. 2016).²⁸

Despite all the overwhelming evidence that secular vocations may face, the Holy Spirit empowers pastors and Christians to endure. This is not endurance by ordinary means but the God-given passion of His calling. The aforementioned data was relevant and supports using wisdom and balance when leading God's people.

In Galatians 5:22-23, Paul wrote, "But the fruit of the Spirit is love, joy, peace, longsuffering, gentleness, goodness, faith, meekness, temperance: against such there is no law." This passage is just one of many that spell out part of the duty description of being a Christian or leader of Christians. The nine qualities of the fruit of the Spirit are easy to read but a challenge to live through in Christians daily lives.

The quality mentioned is love. Love and passion are intertwined. There must be love and passion, a love for God and His people. When a person's passion starts to dwindle, that indicates that the person needs to step back and get to the root of the problem. As mentioned previously, some simple issues could be burnout, family, medical issues, or an inconsistent prayer life, only to name a few.

Whether a person is a Christian or non-Christian, life is never easy. Mental and emotional challenges come regardless of race, ethnicity, or nationality. Moving beyond the idea of cause and effect, all Christians must learn to respond instead of reacting. A reaction is impromptu. The problem or concern has not been reasoned with or meditated upon.

On the other hand, a response (more than likely) has considered all the mitigating

²⁸ Laura Roggenbaum et al., "Secondary Traumatic Stress, Religious Coping, and Medical Mistrust among African American Clergy and Religious Leaders," *Religions* 14, no. 6 (June 15, 2023): 793, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14060793>.

circumstances. Before concluding, all possible outcomes should be considered. This is the same way that Christians are charged to navigate life.

How Christians think, process, and see themselves is extremely important to God. Proverbs 23:7 says, “For as he thinks in his heart, so is he. “Eat and drink!” he says to you, but his heart is not with you.” What this simple verse exemplifies is that our actions come from the heart. How Christians see themselves matters and will harm their lives if it does not align with God’s perspective.

According to Heath Lambert’s *A Theology of Biblical Counseling: The Doctrinal Foundations of Biblical Counseling*:

First John 2:6 says, “Whoever says he abides in him ought to walk in the same way in which he walked.” We saw from Romans 5 that we need Jesus’ righteousness as a human being to represent us in the righteousness we lack. First John teaches that we also need Jesus’ righteous humanity to provide the moral example that we should follow. It is the clear teaching of this passage that those whom Jesus has represented as Savior and who abide in him will be the people who walk as Jesus walked. As we do this, we can have confidence that the same Spirit who empowered obedience in Jesus (Acts 10:38) will empower that same Christlike obedience in our lives as well (Rom. 8:11).²⁹

Lambert’s observations brought to light that empowerment is anchored in obedience. The true sense of empowerment comes from the followers of Christ knowing and embracing His presence. As He is one with the Father, we are one with Him. Although every Christian will have moments and seasons of insecurity, our peace and solace lies within Him, and the residing of the Holy Spirit brings comfort.

God Provided a Means for Humans to Have Balance and Self-care

Throughout the Bible, Christians are encouraged to seek Godly counsel. The

²⁹ Heath Lambert, *A Theology of Biblical Counseling: The Doctrinal Foundations of Biblical Counseling* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2016), chap.5, iBooks.

crucial step for pastors to remember is teaching mental health skillsets will alleviate many of their day-to-day stressors. Pastors often find it almost impossible to detach from the challenges of ministry. The notion of being a Christian 24/7 must be separated from being available 24/7. The goal of every pastor should be to see their congregation empowered by learning to employ mental skillsets. Proverbs 19:20-21 says, “Hear counsel, and receive instruction, that thou mayest be wise in thy latter end. There are many devices in a man's heart; nevertheless the counsel of the LORD, that shall stand.” Counsel is imperative, but there must be balance.

If not careful, pastors and church leaders are prone to merge their identities with their calling and thereby become imbalanced. According to a study written in the *Journal of Pastoral Care and Counseling*:

Having a calling, representing God and modelling His relational qualities to clients meant some participants remained available to clients after hours, especially when the client was in distress. A tension was apparent between the desire and duty to model relational qualities with clients while maintaining boundaries between work and non-work time. The calling brought a perceived pressure to achieve out-comes with clients. Following sessions where they felt clients had not made change or where they felt appropriate therapeutic interventions had not been offered, participants were likely to research interventions or answers in non-work time. Working in non-work time could interfere with hobbies and other activities and at times impacted family members. The sense of being called had participants connect deeply with their clients. As such their clients' stories had an impact on them which continued into non-work time.³⁰

Because God has provided a means for humans to have balance and care for themselves, people should consistently evaluate their physical, spiritual, and mental state.

³⁰ Leanne Frost and Dianne Gardner, “Maintaining Balance for Christian Counsellors When Work Is a Calling,” *Journal of Pastoral Care & Counseling: Advancing Theory and Professional Practice through Scholarly and Reflective Publications* 76, no. 1 (December 27, 2021): 154230502110684, <https://doi.org/10.1177/15423050211068446>.

When addressing the spiritual/mental needs of people, the term “spiritual care” was sometimes used. The article, *From Selfcare to Taking Care of Our Common Home: Spirituality as an Integral and Transformative Healthy Lifestyle*, asserted, “Reflection on spiritual assistance activities in the context of health is not new in the field of theology. However, in general, this assistance has been understood as an activity inherent to pastoral work, regardless of religious confession, although with interesting differences.”³¹

Spiritual care is approached more broadly than a specific religious discipline. From this perspective, it should be understood that the humanistic needs of a person may need to be addressed before their spiritual needs. Jesus turned water into wine and fed over 5,000 people. These two miracles addressed both ordinary physical needs and emotional needs.

In the aforementioned article, the authors also noted:

Spiritual care is thus derived from a concept of “spirituality” that has no necessary relationship with a specific religion. Religiosity can be understood as a form of expression of spirituality linked to some instituted system of religious beliefs and practices. Spirituality already comes from spiritus—breathing; life is related to how the individual seeks and expresses meaning and purpose in life. It has to do with how the person experiences their connection with the moment, with themselves, with others, with nature, with the significant and transcendent other, or with what they consider, in some way, sacred. Spiritual care has been discussed from these basic perspectives in health sciences.³²

From a direct Christian approach, Stuart Briscoe’s *The Preacher’s Commentary Series: Volumes 1 through 35* offered a pragmatic view. In some instances, because Christians are sojourners or pilgrims, and they are sometimes overburdened with trivial

³¹ Alex Villas Boas et al., “From Selfcare to Taking Care of Our Common Home: Spirituality as an Integral and Transformative Healthy Lifestyle,” *Religions* 14, no. 9 (September 13, 2023): 1168, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14091168>.

³² *Ibid.*

things. Christians matter to God, and because of that, He is concerned with their plight.

As Christians mature, their perspective on life should mature as well. Briscoe reinforced his beliefs in this statement:

The Lord Jesus put the whole matter in perspective when He reminded His disciples that earthly values do tend to be superficial while only heavenly values are substantial. He insisted, “Do not lay up for yourselves treasures on earth, where moth and rust destroy and where thieves break in and steal; but lay up for yourselves treasures in heaven, where neither moth nor rust destroys and where thieves do not break in and steal” (Matt. 6:19–20). This pilgrim mentality affects the approach to life, death, possessions, and relationships. When this life is regarded as permanent and significant then all that matters is the here and now.³³

Briscoe brought forth valid points. To achieve balance, everything cannot be a priority. Jesus addressed this to ensure His followers understood that this life was not the finale. In the same breath, balance is contingent upon proper prioritization. As mentioned before, ministry can lead to mental fatigue and burnout. Christians are charged to conduct spiritual business in a physical body. This comes in addition to their families, vocation, and other demands of life. Hartness M. Samushonga made this observation in the *Journal of Pastoral Theology* regarding Moses:

Exodus 18:13-27 offers one of the earliest biblical examples that demonstrates how ministers can become consumed by ‘pastoral’ work – thereby exposing them to the risk of work-related stress and burnout. This passage is usually considered in view of the aspect of delegation of responsibilities. However, the same passage describes Moses’ ‘pastoral’ practice that could potentially lead to burnout as described it in this article, summarized as excessive and prolonged stress resulting from work that involves helping other people, which is characterized by feelings of EE, DP and lack of PA in the work. In the passage, Moses plays the pastoral role of single-handedly meditating disputes among the people.

Based on the size of the population, it is likely that Moses carried out this task more regularly. This threatened his emotional and physical wellbeing. His father-

³³ Briscoe, Stuart. *The Preacher’s Commentary Series, Volumes 1-35: Genesis - Revelation*. Nashville, Tennessee: Thomas Nelson, 2010, chap.1, eBooks.

in-law's (Jethro) was also concerned about Moses' wellbeing when he observed Moses' practice.³⁴

For leaders, attempting to achieve balance is impossible without delegating authority. In addition to delegating authority, the temptation to micro-manage must be resisted. For some leaders, a lack of trust in subordinate leaders can stifle their growth and cause even more stress for the leader. For leaders, this trust factor is exemplified by having faith in God and in the people that God has entrusted them.

Every person's spirit, body, and soul are equally important to God. Because of this, every facet of their being requires maintenance and care. Often, Christians fail to have the "total man" ministered to. Eventually, this can lead to gaps within the lives of believers. In 1 Thessalonians 5:23, Paul wrote, "And the very God of peace sanctify you wholly; and I pray God your whole spirit and soul and body be preserved blameless unto the coming of our Lord Jesus Christ."

Kristen Poppa's *Self-Care is Soul Care*, the Journal of Spiritual Formation and Soul Care asserted:

It wasn't until I read those verses numerous times that I had my "aha" moment. As people made in the image of God, we must take care of our entire being. 1 Thessalonians 5:23 describes how God sanctifies us through and through, including our "whole spirit, soul, and body." As a result, at the heart of soul care is self-care.³⁵

From a Biblical premise, self-care is nothing new. At best, it has been routinely overlooked or demised. What part of man would a loving God leave unattended? The

³⁴ Hartness M. Samushonga, "Distinguishing between the Pastor and the Superhero: God on Burnout and Self-Care," *Journal of Pastoral Theology* 31, no. 1 (July 13, 2020): 4, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10649867.2020.1748919>.

³⁵ Kristen Poppa, "Self-Care Is Soul Care," *Journal of Spiritual Formation and Soul Care* 12, no. 1 (October 17, 2018): 50, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1939790918795633>.

challenge of church leaders in not only to study the Scriptures, but to be intentional in their studies. The “whole spirit” implies that there are parts of the human spirit that can be ignored or neglected. When the spirit is not ministered to in its totality, wholeness becomes incomplete. Because the behavior in people varies, it may be more evident in some than others. It is equally important to realize that every culture is different. Shared experiences and how a culture or group reacts to an incident can leave a lasting impact.

Tonya D. Armstrong’s *African-American Congregational Care and Counseling: Transcending Universal and Culturally Specific Barriers* stated:

In fact, African-American Christians may express even more suspicion towards such forms of care. There are typically two distinct components underlying these suspicions. First, media portrayals of the mentally ill often highlight persons with severe and persistent mental illnesses, such as schizophrenia or bipolar disorder. When mental health care is associated only with the most extreme forms of mental illness, the general public understandably concludes that psychotherapy or counseling are forms of treatment for persons suffering from hallucinations, delusions, or intense mood swings. In the cultural context of mental health care typically manifesting as psychiatric hospitalization or institutionalization, African Americans experiencing even relatively mild forms of psychological struggle are often discouraged by family, community or church members from seeking assistance from a mental health professional. Moreover, some media portrayals have normalized psychotherapy, but primarily for upwardly mobile socioeconomic echelons (e.g. the classic YAVIS patient – Young, Attractive, Verbal, Intelligent, Successful; Schofield, 1986). While trends are shifting, many African Americans associate the need for psychotherapy as reflective of weakness when the subculture emphasizes the need for strength (e.g. Thompson et al., 2004; Walker-Barnes, 2014).³⁶

Instances such as this are indicative of the need for mental health skillsets to be taught within African American churches. God has always desired for Christians to be

³⁶ Tonya D. Armstrong, “African-American Congregational Care and Counseling: Transcending Universal and Culturally-Specific Barriers,” *Journal of Pastoral Care & Counseling: Advancing Theory and Professional Practice through Scholarly and Reflective Publications* 70, no. 2 (June 2016): 118, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1542305016634666>.

able to care for themselves. This can only be accomplished through prayer, education, edification, and an understanding of Scripture.

CHAPTER 4

THEORETICAL PRESUPPOSITION

The African American Experience Develops Resiliency

As consequence of being descendants of enslaved people, many African Americans still feel and experience some of the pain and stigma from it today. The idea of rest is not only associated with sleep. Rest is also anchored in relaxation. Hence, many African Americans, especially in urban cities and southern states, are in constant anxiety. This anxiety can manifest from a plethora of common day-to-day occurrences.

Historically, many African Americans have been treated within healthcare systems with contempt and suspicion. According to Harriett A. Washington's *Medical Apartheid: The Dark History of Medical Experimentation on Black Americans from Colonial Times to the Present*, during slavery:

‘Owners relied upon doctors to tell them whether slaves were malingering, but physicians were less than objective. Dr. W. H. Taylor, called in consultation for an enslaved man, prefaced his assessment with the phrase ‘remembering that simulation was a characteristic of his race.’¹³ Doctors and owners wrote articles in which they shared medical ruses and techniques calculated to get blacks, healthy or not, back into the fields. Dr. M. L. McLoud even wrote his master's thesis on the fraudulent illnesses of slaves.³⁷

Because of countless instances such as this, a deep-rooted distrust between African Americans and the medical field has remained. For some, to seek out mental healthcare appears to be yet another insurmountable obstacle.

According to an article in the *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, *Defining Racial and Ethnic Disparities in THA and TKA*:

³⁷ Harriett A. Washington, *Medical Apartheid: The Dark History of Medical Experimentation on Black Americans from Colonial Times to the Present*. (New York: Random House, 2010).

Race- and ethnicity-based healthcare disparities have been well established by numerous studies in the literature, in health care generally and in orthopaedics specifically. A 2005 Institute of Medicine report confirmed racial and ethnic minorities receive lower-quality health care and have poorer health outcomes than their white counterparts in the United States [46]. In 2004, the Sullivan Commission concluded racial and ethnic minorities, especially African Americans, Latinos, Native Americans, and some Asian Pacific Islander subpopulations, experience higher rates of illness, disability, and premature death than whites [12]. On average, African Americans have the worst health profile among the racial/ethnic groups. The literature provides numerous examples of race-based disparities both in general access to care issues and regarding usage of specific therapies [5, 10, 39, 43].³⁸

Suicide has also remained another uncomfortable topic among African Americans. Because of the lack of formally implemented mental health skillsets, it is rare to find a proactive stance or program of prevention. Regarding post-suicide counseling, Mary Crenshaw's article, *Attitudes of African American Clergy Regarding the Postvention Needs of African American Suicide Survivors* exclaimed:

For example, many suicide survivors reported that African American churches were not comfortable with dealing openly with the suicide of family members (Barnes 2006), and suicide survivors collectively believed that clergy were not helpful (Flarity 1993). Furthermore, another study (Malikow 1991) reported that out of 66 pastors, more than one third were either minimally prepared or not prepared to provide postvention assistance to suicide survivors. Lack of pastoral training in suicide survivor bereavement is problematic, as African Americans normally seek counsel from their clergy during times of bereavement and often do not seek counseling from other professionals external to the church.³⁹

This lack of follow-up can only serve to exacerbate an already volatile situation. Ultimately, whether ill-equipped or uneducated, if the leaders of congregations are not prepared to address the emotional needs of some of their members, they are failing all of

³⁸ Kaan Irgit and Charles L. Nelson, "Defining Racial and Ethnic Disparities in THA and TKA," *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research* 469, no. 7 (April 6, 2011): 1817, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11999-011-1885-z>.

³⁹ Mary Crenshaw, "Attitudes of African American Clergy Regarding Postvention Needs of African American Suicide Survivors," *Pastoral Psychology* 64, no. 2 (April 1, 2015): 169, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11089-013-0581-1>.

their members. Pastors should not be required to be subject matter experts in psychology, but should remain abreast of current trends, family dynamics, and issues that plague their communities.

Per percentile, the rate of teen suicides within the African American culture has steadily risen over the past decade. This is an alarming trend, especially because mental health is seldom discussed within their churches. According to the *Journal of Family Strengths*:

There has been a large increase of suicide among African Americans that has gone largely unnoticed, making it a hidden endemic. The rate of suicide among African American adolescent children is the highest among all children ages 5-11. This is of importance because, traditionally, African Americans have typically registered lower rates of suicide than other ethnic groups. Also, of importance is that past research suggests that simply being African American has served as a protective factor against suicide (Reed, 2019). The figure listed below demonstrates that incidences of suicide among adolescents for the last two decades.⁴⁰

The aforementioned has served as a glimpse of the relevant concerns within African American communities. From the cradle to the grave, the African American experience has been unique. Although the American slave system ended well over a century ago because it was race-based (visual), it has been more difficult for descendants of the formerly enslaved to live inconspicuously. In the journal *Psychological Thought*, the article, *Investigating Historical Trauma Prevalence and Transmission Pathways among African American: Centering Community Wellness Practices*, reported:

Research (Danzer et al., 2016) supported that African Americans are impacted by White racism which shows up as historical trauma, in ways that match the effects of other interpersonal traumas. The effects impact both individuals and groups,

⁴⁰ Darius Reed and Raymond Adams, "Risk and Protective Factor Specific to African American Youth and Adolescents: A Systematic Review," *Journal of Family Strengths* 20, no. 2 (December 31, 2020), https://digitalcommons.library.tmc.edu/jfs/vol20/iss2/5?utm_source=digitalcommons.library.tmc.edu%2Fjfs%2Fvol20%2Fiss2%2F5&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverPages.

and White psychologists should consider these cultural disruptions as historical trauma and therefore a threat to the basic psychosocial safety and well-being of contemporary African Americans. Consistent with research on PTSD, Danzer et al., (2016) pointed out that modern-day African Americans experience more extreme violence, manifest more severe symptoms and more often meet the criteria for P.T.S.D (p. 356). Notably historical and modern-day African Americans also illustrate resilience and productivity in spite of historical and ongoing racial trauma (Utsey et al., 2007). These core strengths include resilience, resistance, family support, and spirituality which also have historical connotations, serving as resources and coping mechanisms among African Americans (Lum, 2003).⁴¹

One of the chief concerns within African American communities has been its over-policing and race-based stereotypes and stigmas. The vilification of a person solely because of color or other demographics has led to law enforcement being met with suspicion. The journal PLOS One noted:

The murder of George Floyd by police in May 2020 sparked international protests and brought unparalleled levels of attention to the Black Lives Matter movement. As we show, his death set record levels of activity and amplification on Twitter, prompted the saddest day in the platform’s history, and caused his name to appear among the ten most frequently used phrases in a day, where he is the only individual to have ever received that level of attention who was not known to the public earlier that same week. Importantly, we find that the Black Lives Matter movement’s rhetorical strategy to connect and repeat the names of past Black victims of police violence—foregrounding racial injustice as an ongoing pattern rather than a singular event—was exceptionally effective following George Floyd’s death: attention given to him extended to over 185 prior Black victims, more than other past moments in the movement’s history. We contextualize this rising tide of attention among 12 years of racial justice activism on Twitter, demonstrating how activists and allies have used attention and amplification as a recurring tactic to lift and memorialize the names of Black victims of police violence. Our results show how the Black Lives Matter movement uses social media to center past instances of police violence at an unprecedented scale and speed, while still advancing the racial justice movement’s longstanding goal to “say their names.”⁴²

⁴¹ Geraldine Palmer, Todd Rogers, and Nathaniel Wilkins, “Investigating Historical Trauma Prevalence and Transmission Pathways among African Americans: Centering Community Wellness Practices,” *Psychological Thought* 16, no. 1 (April 30, 2023): 16, <https://doi.org/10.37708/psyc.v16i1.699>.

⁴² Henry H. Wu et al., “Say Their Names: Resurgence in the Collective Attention toward Black Victims of Fatal Police Violence Following the Death of George Floyd,” ed. Jonathan Jackson, *PLOS ONE* 18, no. 1 (January 11, 2023): e0279225, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0279225>.

The perception of criminalization because of ethnicity is an inescapable reservation held by many Blacks and other people of color. Episodes of anxiety can stem from a mere traffic stop. Because of this, there is an undercurrent of reservation between African Americans to notify law enforcement, when needed.

Another challenge that has plagued the African American community has been teen pregnancies. The Black family was never formally established in the United States. In most instances, enslaved men were mated to selected females for breeding purposes. Because of this, the idea or foundation of family, commitment, and structure was absent. During slavery, the mother provided for her children, and the father was not ever deemed the head of this clandestine version of a family.

Today, the remanence of this mentality still exists. For example:

In 2010, USA teenage birth rates were nearly double (51.4%) for Black adolescents compared with White and non-Hispanic teenagers (23.6%). Similarly, abortion rates of ACB youths were triple (34.5%) those of White and non-Hispanic teenagers (8.5%).⁵ From 2018 to 2019, teen birth rates decreased by 5.2% and 5.8% in Hispanic and non-Hispanic White women between the ages of 15 and 19 years, respectively; however, only a 1.9% decrease was observed in Black women.⁸ These statistics demands a closer examination of teen pregnancy involvement (TPI) rates and their associated factors within this target population.⁴³

In spite of all the aforementioned daunting statistical data, African Americans have proven that they are resilient. Not because of slavery, but in spite of slavery, they have persevered. According to the data from The Pew Research Center, “About a quarter

⁴³ Emmanuela Ojukwu et al., “Teen Pregnancy Involvement among African, Caribbean and Black Adolescent Boys and Girls: A Scoping Review Protocol,” *BMJ Open* 13, no. 7 (July 1, 2023): e066713, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-066713>.

(26%) of all Black U.S. adults ages 25 and older have a bachelor's degree or more education. As of 2022, another third (32%) have completed some college without obtaining a bachelor's, and roughly four-in-ten (42%) have, at most, graduated from high school (or earned an equivalent such as a GED certificate)."⁴⁴

This not only shows resilience, but it also opens the door to optimism and hope. Another key indicator to future successes are linked to the church. The Pew Research Center indicated that "Two-thirds (66%) of all Black adults identify as Protestant. Roughly one-in-five (21%) are religiously unaffiliated, while smaller shares of adults identify as Catholic (6%), or with other Christian denominations (3%) or non-Christian faiths (3%)."⁴⁵

The resilience of the African American Experience has always channeled through the church. Churches coupled with education can only serve to propel African American communities forward.

Mental Health Involves Understanding Intersectionality

Before intersectionality can be addressed, it should be defined. According to Hira Ali, "intersectionality shows that the world cannot be viewed through a monistic lens; hence, these "intersectional interventions in historical memory" show that "history cannot be told in the singular voice or via the lone, iconic figure"^{54, 46}

⁴⁴ Christine Tamir and Abby Budiman, "Facts about the U.S. Black Population," Pew Research Center's Social & Demographic Trends Project (Pew Research Center, January 18, 2024), <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/fact-sheet/facts-about-the-us-black-population/>.

⁴⁵ Christine Tamir and Abby Budiman, "Facts about the U.S. Black Population," Pew Research Center's Social & Demographic Trends Project (Pew Research Center, January 18, 2024), <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/fact-sheet/facts-about-the-us-black-population/>.

⁴⁶ Hira Ali, "Race and Its Repercussions: An Intersectional Analysis of Colson Whitehead's the Nickel Boys," *New Literaria* 04, no. 02 (January 1, 2023): 38, <https://doi.org/10.48189/nl.2023.v04i2.005>.

Because the world view is not binary or linear, people should always consider what remains to be seen in their peripheral vision and behind them. Historically, laws that were made and legislation that has passed had a detrimental impact on women and African Americans. In an attempt to achieve the American dream, meager things such as voting rights, equal pay, and equal protection under the law have traditionally been met with challenge.

Unlike the Millennials, Generation X and Z have taken a much more active role vocally and politically. Over the past five years, their voices have typically been associated with organizations such as Black Lives Matter. In an attempt to teach and learn from history, many of these liberal-minded young African Americans have supported teaching Critical Race Theory (CRT).

Sociologists Nancy Lopez and Howard Hogan asserted:

Critical race theorists' insight that racism is endemic, part and parcel of the fabric of U.S. laws and society, is also relevant for unraveling the paradoxes and contradictions played out in the U.S. body politic after the hard fought Civil Rights movement and the subsequent legislation, involving all three branches of government. Since the passage of the Civil Rights Act in 1965, year after year, elected state representatives and senators (legislative branch of government) have introduced, legislation to prohibit the collection of race data for the enforcement of civil rights legislation concerning, for example, fair housing.⁴⁷

For African American pastors and churches to excel to their fullest potential, pastors and their congregations must gain a better understanding of intersectionality. Gale A. Yee's periodical, *Thinking Intersectionality: Gender, Race, Class, and the Etceteras of our Discipline*, suggested:

⁴⁷ Nancy López and Howard Hogan, "What's Your Street Race? The Urgency of Critical Race Theory and Intersectionality as Lenses for Revising the U.S. Office of Management and Budget Guidelines, Census and Administrative Data in Latinx Communities and Beyond," *Genealogy* 5, no. 3 (August 17, 2021): 75, <https://doi.org/10.3390/genealogy5030075>.

Intersectional analyses make the fundamental point that we who study and interpret the biblical text have many important facets to our identities that are impacted differently by multiple interacting systems of oppression and privilege. As a method of interpretation, intersectionality presumes that our own unique social locations, our own distinctive fusions of gender, race, class, et cetera, influence our readings of texts and our interpretations of them. It encourages us to think beyond the familiar boundaries of biblical studies to expose the diverse power relations of inequality in the text and uncover subjugated voices that were previously invisible or unheard.⁴⁸

Many African American communities are far-fetched from a Utopian society. As a result, some African Americans have adapted or assimilated to the current standards or trends within their communities. Consequently, an ungodly perception of themselves is more likely to arise. When liquor stores and other resources that promote lascivious behavior are prevalent in their communities, the Holy Spirit and His desire to reign within is challenged.

The charge to live a holy lifestyle can become daunting and cause mental stress because their desire to live is continuously met with temptation. There are some that would quickly dismiss intersectionality, by assuming the African Americans have arrived to equality. Decades after the Tuskegee Experiments have subsided, African Americans are still the target audience of horrendous experimentations. Harriet A. Washington asserted:

Between 1992 and 1997, New York City's New York State Psychiatric Institute (NYSPI) and Columbia University's Lowenstein Center for the Study and Prevention of Childhood Disruptive Behavior Disorders conducted several research studies that sought to establish a link between genetics and violence. They performed experiments upon at least 126 boys, most of whom were between the ages of six and ten, utilizing the drug fenfluramine. Columbia described the population of boys who were given the drug as 44 percent black and 56 percent Hispanic, but this is misleading: Hispanic is an ethnic category, encompassing

⁴⁸ Gale Yee, "Thinking Intersectionally: Gender, Race, Class, and the Etceteras of Our Discipline," *Journal of Biblical Literature* 139, no. 1 (2020): 7, <https://doi.org/10.15699/jbl.1391.2020.1b>.

people of white, black, and mixed race, and ‘all the ‘Hispanic’ boys lived in the Washington Heights area and were black Dominicans,” observed Rudy M. Brown, Charisse Johnson’s lawyer.⁴⁹

African American churches have played somewhat of a significant role in safeguarding their communities. Historically, their churches have been and still are the cornerstone of many, if not most, political activism. Regarding politics and African American churches, Shaonta E. Allen asserted:

The socio-political function of the Black Church was also evident in decades after the Civil Rights Movement (Barber 2015). For instance, Brown and Brown (2003) found that church attendance alone did not impact if Black Christians engaged in political activities, such as voting. Conversely, the study reveals the factor that contributed most to rates of Black political engagement was whether or not the church offered civic resources, such as political discussions and opportunities to join committees. Additionally, research by Pattillo-McCoy (1998) and Barnes (2005) has further revealed the diverse ways Black Church culture has been replicated in the broader Black community for political purposes. Ultimately, Black Christianity in America can be considered a political artifact precisely because the Black American experience has and continues to involve a struggle for power, status, and resources, and the Church has been involved with these struggles in both explicit and implicit ways.⁵⁰

Because intersectionality is multi-faceted, has impacted a plethora of places within African American communities. Approximately 67 percent of African American families are single-parented homes. As a result, the women or single-parented mothers continually wrestle with unique challenges. Consequently, their family units are failing at an alarming rate.

⁴⁹ Harriet A Washington, *Medical Apartheid: The Dark History of Medical Experimentation on Black Americans from Colonial Times to the Present*. (New York: Random House, 2010), chap. 11, iBooks.

⁵⁰ Shaonta Allen, “Is the Black Church Dead?: Religious Resilience and the Contemporary Functions of Black Christianity.,” *Religions* 14, no. 4 (March 1, 2023): NA–NA, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14040460>.

Alexandra N. Hood's article, *Dual Status and Adultification: Black Girls' Lives in Context*, noted:

Scholars have argued that historical racism and aftermath of slavery have resulted in the overrepresentation of Black children in youth-serving systems (Morris, 2016; Roberts, 2022). The Child Welfare System (CWS) and the Juvenile Carceral System (JCS) seek to serve and support children, albeit through different avenues and functions, to improve their overall well-being. A cursory glance at existing research shows Black adolescents are overrepresented in the CWS, JCS, and as those with dual-system involvement (i.e., adolescents who encounter both systems, usually labeled dual status, crossover, or multisystem adolescents; Simmons-Horton, 2020; TCC, 2021). In 2021, Black children made up 13% of the U.S. population yet represented 23% of children in the CWS and 32% of the children who are arrested by the JCS (Children's Bureau, 2021; NAACP, 2022; U.S. Census Bureau, 2021).⁵¹

The statistical data presented has validated the struggle of many Black mothers, many of whom began as teenagers. Because of the institution of slavery, this aftermath can also serve as evidence of the failure of African American families to be assembled. Since enslaved African American "families" were not encouraged or recognized, for many, their last consistent solidified family units were dismantled within the gallows of slave ships.

Regarding African American women, another primary concern has been equal pay. To consider this data does not absolve African Americans from choices, but it brings to light mitigating circumstances such as laws, social hierarchies, and systems that impact self-image and worth.

⁵¹ Alexandra N. Hood, "Dual Status and Adultification: Black Girls' Lives in Context," *ProQuest* 23, no. 1 (2023), <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/dual-status-adultification-black-girls-lives/docview/2888008633/se-2?accountid=33215>.

The Center of Disease Control (CDC) has also conducted extensive research regarding intersectionality within the healthcare system. The Center of Disease Control asserted:

Black and other women of color experience stress due to gendered racism in many environments, including the workplace where they often navigate race and gender barriers in professional spaces. For example, a 2020 study on school leadership found that Black women are more likely to experience racialized and gendered role expectations above and beyond those expected of other leaders. In addition, Black and other women of color tend to be evaluated more harshly than men and White women as they navigate harmful stereotypes at work. For example, although anger is a commonly expressed emotion in the workplace, recent research suggests that when Black women express anger at work, their leadership potential is called into question.⁵²

Although this lack of professional medical treatment has long been purported within African American communities, the CDC's research presents credible and tangible evidence.

Perhaps, one of the most controversial topics surrounding African American churches is the role of their churches regarding politics. Although America believes in the separation of church and state, the church has remained influential in how it is governed. For example, Roe vs Wade cannot be discussed without Biblical sentiments regarding the human body. Along the same line, Christian Nationalism has gained more momentum over the past five years.

Based on statistical data from the Pew Research Center:

Given that tradition, black Americans and white Americans have differing views on the role that political topics such as race relations and criminal justice reform should play in religious sermons, according to a Pew Research Center survey conducted earlier this year, before the killing of George Floyd and the ensuing protests. Six-in-ten black adults (62%) say it is important for houses of worship to

⁵² Shanice Battle and Denise Carty, "Gendered Racism among Women of Color | Blogs | CDC," Center for Disease Control and Prevention, October 6, 2022, <https://blogs.cdc.gov/healthequity/2022/10/06/gendered-racism-among-women-of-color/>.

address “political topics such as immigration and race relations” – including 23% who say covering these topics is “essential.” By contrast, 36% of white Americans say it is important for sermons to deal with these topics, and only 8% say it is essential. Four-in-ten white Americans (42%) say these themes *should not* be discussed in sermons. Hispanics are more divided on this issue than black or white Americans are; about half (53%) say it is important for sermons to cover political issues.⁵³

African American churches have always been where the clarion call for social justice and reform resounded. It is believed that the same God that was with the Israelites as they marched around the walls of Jericho is with them. In the same breath, unfortunately, tell-tale-signs of the origins of the complexities of intersectionality can be traced back to slavery.

In the Christian Education Journal’s, *The Double Consciousness of Blackness and Christianity: Towards a Biblical Intersectionality*, Jaison K. D. McCall addresses “blackness” and the unique perspective that many African American Christians navigate. McCall argued:

Parallel to the original concept of double consciousness, the responsibility of being both Black and Christian can be a challenge as, practically, they are often viewed as separate attributes of the group or individual. In a world where racial identity is detected before spiritual identity, this concept of consciousness illustrates the disunion of one ideal: the Black Christian. The Black or African American Christian, by way of the Black Church, possesses an unparalleled history that is inclusive of, but not limited to, four hundred years of slavery, the Civil Rights era, the Black Power movement, etc. This history gives way for specific opportunities to interact with and make disciples within the Black community. To do so effectively, the disjointed identities of the Black Christian must reconnect as one linked vessel reflecting the *imago Dei*.⁵⁴

⁵³ Besheer Mohamed and Kiana Cox, “Before Protests, Black Americans Said Religious Sermons Should Address Race Relations,” Pew Research Center, June 15, 2020, <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2020/06/15/before-protests-black-americans-said-sermons-should-address-race-relations/>.

⁵⁴ Jaison McCall, “The Double Consciousness of Blackness and Christianity: Towards a Biblical Intersectionality,” *Christian Education Journal: Research on Educational Ministry* 16, no. 2 (July 26, 2019): 328–43, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739891319847694>.

Navigating religion, race, classism, and access to equitable medical care (to include mental health) are mitigating factors and obstacles most African Americans engage daily. McCall skillfully uses a dual perspective of being both “Black and Christian.” Many African Americans or Blacks, even if they do not know of the concept of intersectionality, have lived the experiences of where these lines intersect and are blurred.

Partly because of the residual effects from the African American slave system, black women became and has remained the bedrock of their families. Unlike most other families, within theirs she is depended upon to also be a protector and provider. These two additional responsibilities, coupled with her maternal role, has proven to be an overwhelming task. How Black women cope has had a significant impact on their mental health, physical health, and their families. As a consequence, studies suggest that Black women cope differently than women of other cultures within America.

According to research reported by the International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-Being:

Another way race, class, and gender have intersected to impact wellness among Black women has focused on the effects of gendered racism on psychological distress and the role of Africultural coping style (Thomas et al., 2008). Africultural coping styles were determined through the Africultural Coping Styles Inventory (ACSI; Thomas et al., 2008). According to Thomas and colleagues (Thomas et al., 2008), ACSI measures coping skills that are specific to Black culture and includes cognitive/emotional debriefing (e.g., thought avoidance), spiritual-centred coping (e.g., spirituality), collective coping (e.g., social support), and ritual-centred coping (e.g., praying to a deity). In their sample of 344 Black women, nearly 65% of respondents reported an income that falls within the middle-class income level.⁵⁵

⁵⁵ Quenette L Walton et al., “Mind, Body, and Spirit: A Constructivist Grounded Theory Study of Wellness among Middle-Class Black Women,” *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-Being* 18, no. 1 (December 1, 2023): 2278288, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482631.2023.2278288>.

The aforementioned statistical data has given credence to some of the phobias and apprehension many women of color have today. As in all cultures, the children are the future. In any culture, if the healthcare of women are not prioritized, albeit mental or physical, it will have a devastating impact on the families. According to the *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, “In the United States, Black women are 3 to 4 times more likely to experience maternal mortality than White women. They also face similar disparities in severe maternal morbidity. These maternal health disparities are partly driven by disparities in pre-pregnancy and pregnancy-associated cardiometabolic disease.”⁵⁶

This journal also brought to light that quite often racism can operate from an individual level and a structural level. For clarities sake, they defined the two levels as such:

At the structural level, racial disparities in maternal health outcomes stem from various complex factors, including limited access to healthcare throughout pregnancy, the higher burden of chronic medical conditions, social determinants of health, and unequal distribution of high-quality care. These factors are consequences of broader structural inequities, with structural racism being identified as a root cause of these disparities.

At the individual level, there is a substantial body of literature that has examined the impact of interpersonal racism and social inequities on healthcare-seeking behaviors among Black people in the US. These topics have been raised among

⁵⁶ S Michelle Ogunwole and Habibat A Oguntade, “Health Experiences of African American Mothers, Wellness in the Postpartum Period and beyond (HEAL): A Qualitative Study Applying a Critical Race Feminist Theoretical Framework,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20, no. 13 (July 3, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20136283>.

Black women specifically, and as it relates to prenatal and preconception care utilization.⁵⁷

These two mitigating factors have had a tremendous impact upon African American families. Historically, all women, regardless for race, have fought misogynistic battles. From days of old, such as during the Victorian era when fainting chairs were popular, to current, some males have stereotypically viewed women as inferior or emotionally weak. Professor Marina Morrow's research in *Critical Inquiries for Social Justice in Mental Health*, asserted:

Feminists during the second wave criticized psychology and psychiatry for naturalizing and essentializing women as members of a weaker, more men- tally fragile sex (Caplan, 1987). In the ensuing decades these critiques intensified, and feminists sought to illustrate how patriarchal understandings of sex and gender were manifest in the professional practice of psychiatry (for example, Burstow, 1992; Caplan & Cosgrove, 2004; Penfold & Walker, 1983; Smith & David, 1975; Appignanesi, 2007; Ussher, 1991). Alongside these critiques were writings by women of their personal accounts of mental distress and experiences with psychiatry (for example, Blackbridge & Gilhooly, 1985; Capponi, 1992, 1997, 2003; Millet, 1990; Nana-Ama Danquah, 1999; Shimrit, 1997).⁵⁸

Hence, once race, socioeconomics, and other demographics are added, African American women are systematically placed at a significant disadvantage. The National Library of Medicine have done extensive studies on intersectionality. Based upon their research understanding Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) are essential to reforming and providing adequate healthcare. In some circles, EDI and Critical Race Theory (CRT)

⁵⁷ S Michelle Ogunwole and Habibat A Oguntade, "Health Experiences of African American Mothers, Wellness in the Postpartum Period and beyond (HEAL): A Qualitative Study Applying a Critical Race Feminist Theoretical Framework," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20, no. 13 (July 3, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20136283>.

⁵⁸ Kaori Wada and Alyssa M. West, "Critical Inquiries for Social Justice in Mental Health," *Canadian Journal of Counselling & Psychotherapy / Revue Canadienne de Counseling et de Psychothérapie* 55, no. 1 (April 1, 2021): 183, <https://doi.org/10.47634/cjcp.v55i1.70549>.

are “taboo” topics, and as a result, some issues that could potential be resolved go unattended. The National Library of Medicine stated:

The concepts of equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) have received increasing attention and are highly valued ideas in academic medicine and medical education. A plethora of theories, frameworks and approaches have been applied to better understand how we can improve EDI within healthcare spaces both for patients and healthcare professionals. Such approaches have included cultural competence, cultural humility, and various forms of transformative and critical pedagogies [1,2]. Many aspects of critical theories and frameworks are intrinsically related to the concept of intersectionality. Originating as a fourth wave feminist theory and rooted in Black feminist theory, intersectionality broadly refers to the dynamic and contextually specific ways in which social categorization, power, and prejudice intersect with one another to produce and reproduce systems of oppression [3,4,5]. Intersectionality is a component of Critical Race Theory (CRT) which refers to a legal and analytical framework that examines the ways in which systemic racism is embedded within society and exacerbates inequities [6]. Despite its relevance and increasing interest in the topic, empiric study on how intersectionality is understood and applied in the specific context of medical education is needed [7].⁵⁹

Mental Health Skillsets Aid Teaching, Learning, and Healing

As within other cultures, those that labor in ministry pours out but struggle to get replenished. Often, within the African American community, the lack of replenishment stems from trying to be all things to all people. Because of this, teaching, understanding, and implementing mental health skillsets are vitally important. Employed mental health skill sets will enhance the lives of pastors, church members, and their communities.

In Froma Walsh’s *Spiritual Resources in Family Therapy*, she noted:

Many clinicians in the mental health field are unaware that attempts by the therapeutic community to be neutral, secular, and “aspiritual” have led to therapy being viewed as “antispiritual” by some members of the African American community, particularly those with strong religious beliefs (Hines & Boyd-

⁵⁹ Maham Rehman, Divya Santhanam, and Javeed Sukhera, “Intersectionality in Medical Education: A Meta-Narrative Review,” *Perspectives on Medical Education* 12, no. 1 (January 1, 2023): 517–28, <https://doi.org/10.5334/pme.1161>.

Franklin, 2005; Boyd-Franklin, 2003). this is reinforced when therapists who do not know of the deep spiritual roots in African American culture ignore this key component of their clients' core belief systems. in addition, ministers who would otherwise be powerful referral sources may be reluctant to refer troubled congregants to mental health providers because of the profession's reputation for being narrowly secular. (this may be true also of other cultures with strong religious beliefs.)⁶⁰

Because the African American experience has been unique, a well-thought-out approach is required. What works in one particular instance may need to be tweaked to be successful somewhere else.

The *Journal of Pastoral Care and Counseling* suggested:

Because African Americans use the church as a place for mental health resources, it is important for psychologists and clergy to collaborate on models to help parishioners with their mental health issues, whether through community-based interventions, training for pastors or through referral resources. As church leaders, pastors have significant influence on their parishioners. Pastors have the responsibility to authorize outside resources to access church involvement with its membership. Pastors also frequently revert a large part of their pastoral duties involves counseling. Consequently, the pastor's perceptions and attitudes about mental health can have a major impact on services (both internal and external) that parishioners receive. Collaboration between pastors and mental health providers is idyllic and potentially useful, but there has been a disconnect between the theory of bringing psychologists and clergy together and the actions necessary to make it work (McMinn, et al., 1998; Milstein, et al., 2008; Young, et al., 2003).⁶¹

According to Barbara Peacock's article, *It's Okay to Not Be Okay*:

To break down the institutional norms, June says the black church needs to partner with psychologists and psychiatrists. It's a relationship he says churches are open to, as evidenced by the ongoing development of counseling centers and pastoral care at some churches across the nation. The National Biblical Counselors Association, founded and spearheaded by pastor Willie Richardson, is

⁶⁰ Froma Walsh, *Spiritual Resources in Family Therapy* (New York; London: Guilford, 2010) 143.

⁶¹ Jessica Young Brown and Micah L. McCreary, "Pastors' Counseling Practices and Perceptions of Mental Health Services: Implications for African American Mental Health," *Journal of Pastoral Care & Counseling: Advancing Theory and Professional Practice through Scholarly and Reflective Publications* 68, no. 1 (March 2014): 1-14, <https://doi.org/10.1177/154230501406800102>.

an example. The network of predominantly black churches develops biblical counseling curricula to address parishioners' mental health needs.⁶²

From a Christian perspective, healing should always start at church. When Christ walked the earth, an enormous part of His ministry consisted of healing and bringing comfort. Institutions like the National Biblical Counselors Association are needed. Although they are a predominately African American organization, several others have been great resources for healing as well.

In the book *Is Christianity the White Man's Religion?: How the Bible is Good News for People of Color*, its author, Antipas L. Harris, asserted:

When properly understood, Christianity offers redemption for brokenness. The Christian faith invites everyone to divine identity. Peter reminds believers that 'he who called you is holy, so be holy in all you do; for it is written: 'Be holy, because I am holy'' (1 Peter 1:15-16). In other words, Christ is God's invitation to every human being, regardless of their family situation, social location, ethnic identity, or past life.⁶³

From a cultural point of view, these type of sentiments and exegesis of Scripture have brought hope and teaches the equality of all humanity through Christ. If Christ came to set captives free, it is free in body, mind, and soul. The mind cannot and should not ever be dismissed. When the mind is held captive, the body becomes a shell, and the soul fails to fulfill its divine purpose.

In an article titled, *Where Would You Go? Race, Religion, and the Limits of Pastor Mental Health Care in Black and Latino Congregations*, studies were conducted with both Black and Latino churches comprised of 14 pastors and 20 members in

⁶² Rita Omokha, "It's Okay Not to Be Okay," ChristianityToday.com, October 20, 2020, <https://www.christianitytoday.com/ct/2020/november/black-church-mental-health-trauma.html>.

⁶³ Antipas L. Harris, *Is Christianity the White Man's Religion?: How the Bible Is Good News for People of Color* (Downers Grove, Illinois: IVP, an imprint of InterVarsity Press, 2020), chap. 4, iBook.

Houston, Texas. Although there were similarities and differences, according to Daniel Bolger and Pamela J. Prickett, their studies concluded:

If pastors remain at the forefront of providing mental health care in many racial/ethnic minority communities—a conclusion supported by our results—then equipping pastors to better fill these roles is imperative for providing adequate care. While congregants in our study sought out pastors because of their perceived expertise, pastors lamented their own lack of training in pastoral care and the limits of their ability to care for mentally ill members. This tension only further magnifies the importance of calls for congregations to better connect with mental health care providers (Allen et al. 2010; Dempsey et al. 2016).⁶⁴

This case study has served as evidence that African American pastors need mental health skillsets. There is a great need for them to know the signs of mental fatigue, stress, and burnout. Unless these skillsets and learned and resources are taught, they are ineffective in meeting the requirements of their members.

Bolger and Prickett also noted:

The present study is not without limitations, each of which provides direction for future research on the relationships among religion, race, and mental health. First, while our study was novel in comparing Christians across racial/ethnic groups, the primary churches in our study came from different denominations and theological traditions. This limits our ability to disentangle how the respective racial compositions and theological traditions of each congregation shape perceptions of mental health.⁶⁵

Although Bolger and Prickett believe that denominations may have been a mitigating factor, a myriad of things could also be contributors. According to the book *Religion in the Lives of African Americans: Social, Psychological, and Health*

⁶⁴ Daniel Bolger and Pamela J. Prickett, “Where Would You Go? Race, Religion, and the Limits of Pastor Mental Health Care in Black and Latino Congregations,” *Religions* 12, no. 12 (November 30, 2021): 1062, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12121062>.

⁶⁵ Daniel Bolger and Pamela J. Prickett, “Where Would You Go? Race, Religion, and the Limits of Pastor Mental Health Care in Black and Latino Congregations,” *Religions* 12, no. 12 (November 30, 2021): 1062, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12121062>.

Perspectives, “The three denominations that blacks are most likely to be affiliated with are Baptist, Methodist, and Catholic. Half of all blacks report they are Baptists, and this percentage is consistent across all surveys.”⁶⁶

From a statistical point of view, Monique Morris’, *Black Stats: African American by the Numbers in the Twenty-First Century* suggested:

African Americans are 20 percent more likely than Whites to report feeling serious psychological distress. African Americans make up 4 percent of all adults reporting serious psychological distress, but that percentage doubles for African Americans below the poverty line.²¹ Black children in households below the poverty line are more likely to be diagnosed with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD): 17 percent of Black children ages 5 to 17 living in poverty are diagnosed with ADHD, compared to 13 percent of all youth living in poverty. Black Americans make up 12 percent of single-race adults who experience feelings of sadness, worthlessness, and hopelessness. Multiracial Black adults make up 19.6 percent of all people of two or more races who report such feelings.²² 9 percent of Black adults feel that everything is an effort, compared with 5 percent of White adults.²³ Black full-time college students and their similarly situated Black counterparts out of college experienced a major depressive episode in the past year at similar rates, 7 percent and 6 percent, respectively.^{24 67}

From some, these statistics may not seem alarming, but they are indicative of a constant mental health problem within African American culture. Perhaps one of the easiest mental health concerns that all people should attempt to manage are their emotions. How a person emotes can have detrimental effects, both physically and psychologically. If a person is a leader, parent, or coworker, it will have some type of impact on all parties involved. Regarding anger, G. S. Baker suggested:

People can interpret situations differently, so a situation that makes you feel very angry may not make someone else feel angry at all (for example, other reactions

⁶⁶ Taylor, Robert J, Linda M Chatters, and Jeff Levin, *Religion in the Lives of African Americans* (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, 2003), 22.

⁶⁷ Monique W Morris, *Black Stats: African Americans by the Numbers in the Twenty-First Century* (New York: The New Press, 2014), chap. 5, iBooks.

could include annoyance, hurt or amusement). But just because we can interpret things differently, it doesn't mean that you're interpreting things 'wrong' if you get angry. How you interpret and react to a situation can depend on lots of factors in your life, including:

- Your childhood and upbringing
- Past experiences
- Current circumstances
- Life Events
- Thinking Styles
- Behavioral Explanations
- Evolutionary Reasons
- Biological Reasons⁶⁸

Baker's sentiments towards how people should process emotions, are not without merit. Regardless of nationality, race, or ethnicity, we all experience anger and a plethora of other emotions. How people process and handle their feelings will either prove beneficial or detrimental.

Beyond Christianity, many professionals believe that religious belief systems, in general, can benefit the emotional and mental healing process. Some people may identify as spiritual but do not claim any specific belief system, or they may claim many variants. According to Harold G. Koenig's and Harvey Jay Cohen's *The Link between Religion and Health: Psychoneuroimmunology and the Faith Factor*:

If religious beliefs and practices improve coping, reduce stress, and increase hope and optimism, then there is a reason to think that religion might also affect the speed of wound healing and ultimately influence surgical outcomes, such as longer walking distances after hip surgery (Pressman et al., 1990), greater survival after open-heart surgery (Oxman et al., 1995), and improved health after heart transplantation (Harris et al., 1995). A few studies report less need for pain medication and shorter hospital stays after surgery for patients who receive

⁶⁸ G S Baker, *Emotional Intelligence Master Your Emotion-2 Books in 1-* (G. S. Baker, 2019), chap. 1, iBooks.

religious interventions, particularly chaplain visits (Bliss et al., 1995; Florell, 1973).⁶⁹

In many regards, Koenig and Cohen have group all religions together, hence rendering Christianity a mere placebo. There are many pastors and clergy that would challenge their position. After all, embracing this position would undermine the entire earthly ministry of Christ. This approach would render Him no more than a snake oil salesman.

In the book *Psychology and the Church: Critical Questions, Critical Answers*, Dave Hunt and T.A. McMahon are a lot more cynical of Christians seeking psychological help. Hunt and McMahon proclaim, “The litmus test of truth for victorious Christian living must be: Is derived from Scripture, or is it the wisdom of this world packed in Christian terminology to make it appear compatible with Scripture?”⁷⁰ Their premise has remained that Psychology offers a new source of truth other than Christ. They are skeptical, at best, about Christians receiving counseling or therapy outside of the church.

Hunt and McMahon also asserted:

Christian psychology, however, derived not from Scripture but from humanistic sources, makes convenient and justifies on ‘scientific’ grounds the ‘I can’t’ excuse. It covers all manner of sins as only love is supposed to do (Proverbs 10:12). And in the delusive process, self-esteem is salvaged (isn’t that to psychology credit?). The unfaithful spouse doesn’t need to feel guilty after all because the lie of self-love has given her or him convenient justification.⁷¹

⁶⁹ Harold Koenig and Harvey Cohen, *The Link between Religion and Health: Psychoneuroimmunology and the Faith Factor* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2002), 133.

⁷⁰ Dave Hunt and T A McMahon, *Psychology and the Church: Critical Questions, Crucial Answers* (Bend, Ore.: Berean Call, 2008), 93.

⁷¹ Dave Hunt and T A McMahon, *Psychology and the Church: Critical Questions, Crucial Answers* (Bend, Ore.: Berean Call, 2008), 92.

Their perception and approach toward Christians seeking psychological help undervalues and undermines a great resource for healing. In retrospect, a person that was visually impaired should have never gone to an optometrist. Because God is a God that is concerned with healing, the human mind should not be omitted.

Contrary to Hunt and McMahon's opinions, many other sources suggest communities such as the African Americans and other marginalized communities could benefit from counseling. One of the key components for undertakings such as this would be trust. If there is a lack of trust, people will approach counseling with inhibitions, if at all.

The National Library of Medicine suggested:

In addition to spirituality and religion, education about mental illness, diagnosable disorders, effects of psychotropic medication and the treatment process is critical to reducing barriers to treatment within the African American community. White established suggestions for overcoming this barrier by recommending public education campaigns (e.g., mass media), educational presentations at community venues (e.g., Black churches), and open information sessions at local mental health clinics. Implementation of these campaigns will not only provide much needed education but also provide opportunities to lessen the stigma and taboo of discussing, acknowledging and accepting mental health concerns within the African American community especially as it relates to the symptoms and effects of racial trauma. It is also important to note that the facilitators of these educational campaigns must come from the African American community in order to build trust in the mental health system.⁷²

Without trust, neither learning nor healing can take place. The National Library of Medicine's observations conveyed the imperativeness of having leaders at the helm from within their own communities. A valid part of trust is seeing people within your communities that are known, respected, and equipped with mental health skillsets and modeling it.

⁷² Angela M. Grayson, "Addressing the Trauma of Racism from a Mental Health Perspective within the African American Community," *Delaware Journal of Public Health* 6, no. 5 (November 2020): 28, <https://doi.org/10.32481/djph.2020.11.008>.

Learning and implementing coping strategies are essential. Because the African American experience is unique within itself, stressors and coping strategies may somewhat differentiate from some other races. First, how these commonly stressors occur should be considered before addressing coping mechanism or strategies.

Based upon information attained from the National Library of Medicine:

We found that the type of racist experience determined to a great extent which type of strategy people reported using. We identified three distinct levels of racism in the studies: cultural (i.e., assertion of Eurocentric Western values and practices resulting in the exclusion or denigration of other histories and traditions), interpersonal (i.e., biases that occur when an individual's racialized beliefs affect their interactions with people of color), and institutional (i.e., differential access to goods, services, and opportunities based on perceived racial identity; see Fig. 2; Haeny et al., 2021; J. M. Jones, 1999).⁷³

Based upon their findings, the three mitigating factors that causes stress for most African Americans, in regard to race, are cultural, interpersonal, and institutional. This racial paradigm creates barriers many African Americans find difficult to overcome or circumvent. Some studies have suggested African American men and women employ different coping strategies. The Journal of Black Psychology indicates:

General experiences of racism have been examined among African American men. These studies have also generally been designed to determine the influence of gender in understanding racism-related coping responses (e.g., Greer et al., 2009). For instance, in some studies, African American women have been shown to utilize emotion-based strategies to address racism (e.g., Greer, 2011; Shorter-Gooden, 2004), while some evidence suggests that African American men engage in more problem solving to address racism (e.g., Mosley et al., 2017); albeit they are less likely to seek social support compared with African American women (e.g., Mincey, Alfonso, Hackney, & Luque, 2015). Lewis-Coles and Constantine (2006) reported a similar pattern of findings in the use of religious coping to address racism-related experiences. They found that African American women utilized greater deferring (i.e., waiting on a Higher Power to intervene) and collaborative religious coping (i.e., the individual and a Higher Power are

⁷³ Grace Jacob and Sonya Faber, "A Systematic Review of Black People Coping with Racism: Approaches, Analysis, and Empowerment," *Perspectives on Psychological Science* 18, no. 2 (August 25, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.1177/17456916221100509>.

responsible for resolution) than men in their sample. Men reported greater use of self-directing religious problem solving (i.e., reliance on self for resolution) than women (Lewis-Coles & Constantine, 2006).⁷⁴

In short, because African American churches have remained one of the most influential systems of hope, many African American women tend to rely on their faith in God. With that being said, this fact alone is indicative of the urgency of African American pastors to be equipped with mental health training and knowing the proper resources within their communities.

⁷⁴ Tawanda M. Greer and Klaus E. Cavalhieri, "The Role of Coping Strategies in Understanding the Effects of Institutional Racism on Mental Health Outcomes for African American Men," *Journal of Black Psychology* 45, no. 5 (July 2019): 405, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095798419868105>.

CHAPTER 5

PROJECT PLANS AND OBJECTIVES

Specific Objectives for the participants and myself will be categorized as: (1) cognitive, which pertains to learning new information or insight; (2) affective, regarding perceptions and attitudes, motivation, and values; or (3) skills, which has to with demonstration of the ability or performance. The objectives emphasis were on demonstratable change as recorded as outcomes in the project.

Participants' Objectives

There were three specific measurable objectives for the project participants:

First, as a cognitive objective, the pastors would demonstrate a better understanding of spirituality and psychology. Pastors would achieve this outcome through:

- a. Distinguishing between spirituality and psychology
- b. Demonstrating basic psychology and mental health
- c. Demonstrating an understanding from a developmental perspective

Second, as an affective objective, the pastors would convey openness by expressing personal feelings and values about mental health. Pastors would accomplish this outcome through:

- a. Discussing Biblical human psychology with the class and other appropriate people
- b. Completing mental health and emotional issues homework and discussing feelings in class
- c. Actively participating in the pastors' support group activities.
- d. Using and discussing Biblically based human psychology and mental health books, in spite of feelings of awkwardness

- e. Using teachable moments to address mental health issues in families regardless of possible feelings of embarrassment or discomfort

Third, as a skill-related objective, the pastors would show improvement in communication mental health skillsets with their leaders. Pastors would demonstrate this outcome through:

- a. Using active listening skills
- b. Using Biblical wording and its contemporary syntax to ensure clarity
- c. Using problem-solving mental health skillsets to process emotional issues
- d. Using psychological terminologies in their ministries
- e. Identifying and using additional mental health resources as needed

Personal Objectives for the Project

I had a cognitive and skill-oriented personal objective to accomplish by the conclusion of this project:

First, I would clarify my personal theological and theoretical positions regarding mental health from a Biblical perspective. I would evidence this through:

- a. Identifying appropriate Bible verses that reveals Godly mindsets for pastors and members
- b. Conducting thorough research to explore my positions in depth
- c. Writing clear and concise theological and theoretical sections for my project
- d. Integrating my position into the lesson plan

Second, I would demonstrate the ability to teach varied group of pastors as indicated through:

- a. Selecting and writing lesson plans that include a variety of teaching techniques to appeal a wide range of psychological needs

- b. Selecting and using a Christian mental health series that is readily used by those of various educational levels
- c. Facilitating and modeling tolerance for differing positions held by project participants to prevent imposition of my personal position or values upon them

CHAPTER 6

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROJECT

The project consisted of an introductory session and five two-hour sessions held online weekly. I coordinated with three Senior Pastors, whom all consented to participate in this study. Two pastor's ministries were located in Clarksville, TN and the third was located in Albany, GA. At the onset of the selection of participants for the project, each participant conveyed eagerness and considered the topic needed and timely. I explained to each of them that while attempting to satisfy the requirements for the Doctorate of Intercultural Degree, I felt led to address mental health within predominately African American churches.

Since attending Faith International University and pursuing this particular doctoral program, I have learned a enormous amount about various world religions, ideologies, beliefs, and social dynamics. In a nutshell, this program prompted me to examine, in detail, the African American church, its culture, and its approach towards mental health.

Although there is only one Church, the Body of Christ, it has become fragmented due to society, politics, and cultural norms. As a consequence, man-made problems can only yield more man-made problems. In 1 Corinthians 3, the Apostle Paul admonished the church at Corinth for being divisive. Some of the people claimed to be his followers, whereas others claimed to be followers of Apollos. Immediately Paul reprimanded this type of mindset and behavior. Less than half of a millennium after this letter to the church in Corinth was written, different schools of thought would eventually evolve into what is now known as denominations. Beyond mere culture, race, class, and gender are common

arguments in many of today's reformations and denominations. All things considered, historically, many African American churches were born from an outward cry towards God and as a traumatic response to society.

Perhaps two of the most profound books I read during this program were H. Richard Niebuhr's, *Christ and Culture* and James S. Cone's, *The Cross and the Lynching Tree*. Niebuhr's book compelled me to pause and seriously consider to the role of Christ within our society and His influence and proper place within our culture. His pragmatic view concluded that we as Christians will see Christ from one of five perspectives: Christ Against Culture; Christ of Culture; Christ Above Culture; Christ in Paradox; and Christ the Transformer of Culture. Regardless of race, creed, denominational affiliation, or ideology, each person professing Christ is compelled to choose, if nothing more than by deeds.

On the other hand, I found Cone's book to be equally captivating. Unlike Niebuhr's book, which was required, Cone's book was supplemental. Cone's book captured the essence of the Black church and the struggle between faith and society. He showed a lot of symbolism and connections between the sufferings of Christ and the victimizations and exploitations of the African American Experience during and post-slavery.

After reading both books, I quickly deduced that both authors, whose books were written about sixty years apart, loved and served the same God. Both men turned not only to the same God but also read the same Bible to find answers to problems within their cultures. With that being said, I believe that the answers are still in the Bible, but every generation must seek God to help remedy the problems it faces.

Prior to the implementation of the project, two participants shared with me that they had always prayed something of this magnitude regarding mental health would be initiated. They both exclaimed that there were times when they felt ill-equipped regarding mental health issues. From this informal discussion, one of the two participants shared that he had recently had a lengthy conversation with one of his church members who has bipolar disorder. He stated that in the past, being bipolar may have been dismissed as a “spirit,” and his church member could have gone through life undiagnosed. With that being said, all participants agreed that approaching the Bible from a mental health perspective would enhance their comfort with the topic and the lives of their members.

I found the Center of Disease Control’s (CDC) website’s information, resources, and statistical data on mental health invaluable. Another invaluable website and resource was Mental Health America. I found the tests on Mental Health America’s website, which includes tests on Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), bipolar, addiction, self-injury, and eating disorders invaluable. In addition, the Moody College of Communication had extensive PowerPoint presentations that aided in preparation and training.

Among other things, the Harvard Business Review contained a treasure trove of information regarding the three aspects of active listening. Another phenomenal resource was the Brain and Behavior Research Foundation. Their content alone provided solid academic insight regarding a plethora of topics ranging from depression to coping strategies. Because of these resources and more, I was better able to create lesson plans, discussion material, and homework assignments.

I found the Wisconsin Department of Public Instruction's lesson plans on Mental Health Literacy extremely useful and a vital resource throughout the project. The Mental Health Literacy lesson plan contained invaluable information regarding how to establish dialogue about mental health, responding to stress, stress management, and establishing boundaries. Their lesson plan and the previously mentioned resources gave the project the girth it needed to appeal to all psychological types and teaching styles. Because this was conducted in an online format, I utilized my resources by sharing my screen and emailing or texting links to materials. Other invaluable resources were Anthony Evans' and Stacey Kaiser's book, *When Faith Meets Therapy*⁷⁵ and information from the National Alliance on Mental Illness (NAMI).

In order to appeal to a wide range of psychological types and maintain participants' interest, I used a variety of teaching techniques and methodologies during this research project. Several of the teaching techniques I used during the project were group discussions, lectures, and homework assignment discussions. In addition, I also ensured the Bible studies were relevant and could relate to the theoretical materials presented and the African American experience. All participants held a minimum of a master's degree and were seminary graduates.

To protect and preserve the participants' privacy and confidentiality, I did not retain any sensitive information shared during the sessions or in homework assignments. The initial session was conducted online on Thursday January 18, 2024, and held weekly thereafter.

⁷⁵ Anthony Evans and Stacy Kaiser, *When Faith Meets Therapy* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2022).

The initial session of the research project was done online in GoToMeeting. A pretest on mental health was administered. Because all meetings were virtual, I ensured all participants received digital copies of all course work and materials ahead of time. Each participant found our weekly scheduled sessions conducive to their schedules. Since all participants were pastors and one resides in another state, they all found the online format to be conducive to their busy schedules. In order to build trust and to preserve the participants' anonymity, I did not retain any specific sensitive shared during the homework session or assignments. As a further measure of confidentiality, I assigned each participant a number (P1, P2, and P3), in lieu of their names. Although the project was centric to the African American experience, the theological principles were universal. With that being said, I analyzed and evaluated the sessions from that perspective in the final chapter of this report.

Additionally, in the initial session after opening with prayer, during the first hour, I presented an overview of the course material and topics that would be addressed over the next several weeks. After an icebreaker and discussing the goals and objectives of the project, the pastors formally consented to be participants. Hence, all pastors filled out and signed a Participant's Enrollment and Personal History Form (EPHF)⁷⁶.

In addition, they signed a learning covenant committing themselves to fulfill the participants' project requirements. Due to the hospitalization of one of my family members, and the death of one of the participants' grandmother-in-law, we agreed to the dates of our weekly meetings as being tentative. The participants agreed fully to participate, complete all reading assignments, and to prayerfully apply elements of what

⁷⁶ See Appendix 10, 101.

they would learn, as they progressed. Once the covenants were signed, I administered a Modified Mental Health Knowledge Inventory (MMHKI)⁷⁷ to all three participants. I closed the session with prayer.

In the second session, I utilized materials and online resources to aid the participants in exploring and understanding their own mental health. I ensured that each participant filled out a Participant's Period Feedback Form (PPFF)⁷⁸ for the previous week. I opened the session with prayer and conducted a review of the project agreement and significant points within the covenant.

The next activity was individual Bible study based on mental health, which afforded the pastors an opportunity to explore and understand their own psychological makeups. The key topics were a warm-up activity, a Bible study, and an introduction and exploration of mental health. The Bible study consisted of reviewing 1 Thessalonians 5:23. The emphasis of this discussion explored the concept of man having a spirit, soul, and body. Biblical characters, such as Moses, Jeremiah, and Paul were used as examples of prominent leaders who sometimes struggled with depression and anxiety. The discussion that followed demonstrated that even though a person can be called by God, no one is exempt from seasons of struggle or bouts with depression. A lot of emphasis was made on the soul of man and how people see themselves will have an enormous amount of influence upon their emotions. With that being said, I was able present to them a more refined view of the reason our mental health is important to God. I also stressed

⁷⁷ See Appendix 7, 96.

⁷⁸ See Appendix 5, 94.

the importance of our thoughts as Christians to be aligned with what God's mandates for our lives.

I gave copies of appendices 1 to 3 and homework assignments regarding exploring one's own mental health. I closed the session with an emphasis on, it is Okay for leaders not to be Okay. After emphasizing it is not God's desire for us to remain permanently in a state of hopelessness or depression, but to seek Him and help from others, I closed in prayer.

The third session addressed the homework from session two. I addressed some of the various ways mental health issues can manifest. Each participant had filled out a PFFF. I opened our meeting with prayer and conducted a brief review of the previous session's materials. The group discussed the homework assignments from the previous week. The pastors were able to make a correlation between the tri-union Godhead and all men have three distinct parts. Our Bible study was based upon Proverbs 11:14, Philippians 4:6-7 and 2 Timothy 1:7. I emphasized that being anxious or struggling with anxiety is a part of human nature. Likewise, fear can be a human response to trauma, but not a God-given way to live. I concluded this discussion by giving a Biblical example of the benefits of having counselors.

Within the bulk of discussion, it was concluded that basic anxiety was unavoidable and inevitable and that triggers vary. Ultimately, regardless of the problem, God's word should always be consulted. The group explored exercises dealing with common mental health concerns to include bipolar, schizophrenia, substance abuse, panic disorders, and depression and its triggers. I also gave participants supplemental resources addressing all the aforementioned topics during the session. I then returned the MMHKI

results to each participant and conducted a review of the answers. The group then examined the perceptions and misconceptions of mental health illnesses and how it should be approached when talking about mental health concerns. After this, I assigned homework to evaluate each participant's confidence in addressing mental health concerns. I closed the session in prayer.

The fourth session dealt with race, gender, and intersectionality. After praying and the completion of the PPF, the group discussed the previous week's homework assignments. The initial discussions emphasized the profound impact race, gender, and socioeconomics have within society, and, in turn, how these discriminatory mitigating factors can also have a psychological impact. I then led the participants in a discussion regarding how they might approach discussing race-related trauma with the aggrieved without vilifying any specific race or group. I led a group discussion on intersectionality and the psychological impact of systemic racism. The group were made aware of the complexities of intersectionality. To add more insight to the discussion, I also presented handouts for each participant. Based upon scholarly research, we discussed why not addressing race, gender, and intersectionality, or attempting to repress emotions may have detrimental psychological consequences.

After this discussion, I led a Bible study based on John 4:1-26. I emphasized how the woman who Jesus met at the well had experienced systemic discrimination. I also explained that the word intersectionality is not in the Bible, but it encapsulates the same dynamics and intricacies. I explained how, even in complexed and cultural situations, God is still ever present, cares, and involved within His creation. To emphasize an example of the concept of intersectionality in the Bible, I used the Apostle Paul. I pointed

to the fact that twice in Scripture, Acts 16:37-38 and Acts 22:25-28, although Paul identifies as a Jew, he was also a Roman citizen. Paul had faced adversity because of the Roman system emplacement. Consequently, to receive justice, he made it known that he was not only a Jew but also a Roman citizen. This discussion and the Biblical examples helped them to better understand the terminology and its application. Towards the end of the Bible study, each participant shared how they saw the relevancy of these particular examples and how it pertained to their ministries or communities.

Prior to concluding our session, I assigned homework to aid the pastors in becoming more aware and seizing teachable moments in their churches. I closed in prayer.

The fifth session focused on coping skills. After opening in prayer, we discussed the prior sessions homework. I then discussed the importance of learning and employing coping skills. The group explored how to process and control emotions in a way to their beneficial to their overall mental health. During this session, I made an emphasis on the need for strategies to be precalculated and known how and when to be employed. Furthermore, that coping skilling requires a proactive approach towards stress and trauma, by responding instead of reacting. In addition, the group examined effective ways to cope with stress for better mental health outcomes. Some of the coping strategies discussed were as follows: (1) practicing self-care and prioritizing time, (2) engaging in activities or hobbies that relieve stress, (3) meditation and prayer, and (4) disconnecting from electronics and social media. I then transitioned to discussing the principle of the Sabbath. The group discussion evolved around what brought each participant pleasure and relaxation. In addition, I led the Bible study based on Philippians 4:4-7. From a

theological perspective, I emphasized the importance of prayer; petitioning God regarding our concerns; and, by faith, thanking Him in advance because it is only through these seasons authentic faith grows. I summarized the discussion by encouraging each participant to draw clear and concise decisions to prioritize time for relaxation and unplugging by employing coping strategies consistently.

Towards the end of the session, I recommended that the participants continue to incorporate mental health skillsets within their ministries. I assigned homework and closed with prayer.

The sixth session consisted of opening in prayer and an initial emphasis upon the importance of listening skills as well as a review of the five previous sessions to include the last sessions homework. The primary focus was on skillsets learned and implemented. Each participant filled out the PPF. Next, I facilitated a lecture employing proper listening skills. I explained that without exhibiting sincere listening skills, that members would be less likely to open up or share during counseling. Each participant was presented with materials that addressed the importance of employing the three aspects of active listening skills, which are the following: (1) cognitive, (2) emotional, and (3) behaviour.

To further enhance the topic of listening skills, I facilitated a Bible study using James 1:9 as a primary verse. During this discussion, I emphasized the importance of “being slow to speak and quick to listen.” I explained that quite often, pastors and leaders are quick to assume a position prior fully to listening to all input. In addition, I used our prayer lives as an example. I listened to pastors in the study when they were praying in

sessions. Listening is a way of expressing love, compassion, and showing someone that you care.

I also instructed them how to be intentional not to interrupt a person's train of thought. I also stressed the importance of allowing people to be and feel heard and manifest their emotions verbally. During this session, I addressed the need for participants not to take offence and always to exhibit emotional intelligence when counseling. To sum it up, the main movements within the entire Bible study emphasized the importance of listening, of knowing when to speak or interject, and of controlling your own emotions.

After the session concluded, I administered a posttest. Each participant completed a Participant's Personal Goals Form (PPGF)⁷⁹ to project goals for the future following the official class sessions. I concluded the session by thanking the participants for volunteering for the project. All of the participants were reminded of my contact information, and I closed with prayer.

After the completion of this degree program, I suggested meetings be conducted online in a live audio and video format quarterly. I volunteered to become the primary facilitator for the Pastoral Support Group (PSG), if they choose to commit. Because of the enthusiasm of the participants, all participants are looking forward to hosting mental health workshops within their perspectives ministries in the near future.

Following the six weeks of sessions, I compiled all data obtained during the project. After compiling the data, I interpreted the data and wrote my final Doctor of Intercultural Studies Report.

⁷⁹ See Appendix 6, 95.

CHAPTER 7

ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF PROJECT DATA

Evaluation and Assessment Tools

I anticipated that this would be the most challenging portion of the entire project. Many of the projects outcomes could only be derived from the participants' behaviors, especially with respect to the affective objective. I conducted outcome and goal-oriented evaluations of the participants and myself. I also examined the project's overall effectiveness regarding processes perspectives.

To evaluate the cognitive objective of the participants, I used the information gleaned from the Center of Disease Control regarding mental health as a pretest and posttest. This data collected was used to determine if the participants were able to distinguish or identify different types of mental health conditions and psychosis. The mental health pretest and posttest was used to demonstrate the participants' comprehension of basic mental health and psychological knowledge. To demonstrate an understanding of human psychology and the Biblical approach towards mental health numerous Scriptures were used as supporting evidence.

In regard to evaluating the affective objective for participants, several assessment tools were utilized throughout the project. I evaluated the participants' participation during each session for consistency, the manner in which they completed homework assignments, and their comfort level in discussing mental health. In addition, the pastors' level of participation in the informal conversation after sessions served as an additional affective evaluation tool. In addition, participants emailed to the project facilitator the PPF regarding each session. The PPF consisted of questions regarding the following

areas: (1) reading assignments, (2) written assignments, (3) basic session evaluation, (4) teachable moments, and (5) additional comments. Information from the PPFf assisted in evaluating whether pastors were utilizing precepts from the lessons learned within their individual ministries. In addition, it also identified their level of comfort when doing so. The participants also self-assessed the affective perspectives in relation to mental health and psychology.

Class participation highlighted the skill-related objective of participants. The participants' psychological types likely impacted this evaluation. In order to evaluate the participants' need or desire to research information, I suggested several credible and scholarly websites for us to deepen the breath of our discussions. The teachable moments questions on the PPFf aided to substantiate information gathered regarding mental health within their churches. I tested the participants' recognition of mental health and psychological terminologies by utilizing the pretest, posttest, and the PPEF. Class discussion of examples and scenarios served as an evaluative tool regarding different aspects of counseling and mental health concerns related to pastor-and-member interactions. The PPEF contained questions regarding each participants' intention to implement project-evaluated skills.

In evaluating personal objectives for the project, I relied upon the process of planning, conducting, and evaluating the project. The premise of my theological and theoretical views were conveyed consistently throughout the research and writing process for the prospectus and project. I explored my personality and teaching style utilizing the CliftonStrengths Assessment. The PPFf provided consistent feedback to evaluate my relationship to the participants and their attitude towards me and the materials presented.

The end of the project interviews brought clarity regarding the overall process as well as additional insights from each participant to aid in my personal growth.

Analysis and Evaluation of Participants' Data

The first section of this analysis addressed general information regarding the participants. Following this information, I have formatted the analysis to parallel the participants' goals for this project.⁸⁰

To preclude identification of the project participants, I have randomly designated the three male participants as P1 through P3. All participants were Christian senior pastors with ministries and churches in Clarksville, Tennessee and Albany, Georgia. All three participants enrolled for educational purposes and personal growth. Each participant indicated some type of previous formal mental health education experience.

The cognitive objective was for the pastors to demonstrate a greater understanding of the Biblical position regarding mental health. P1, P2, and P3 indicated a concise understanding of mental health indicated by the following scores in Table 1:

Table 1. Analysis of Pretest and Posttest for the Modified Mental Health Knowledge Inventory

Participants	Pretest Score	Posttest Score	Change
P1	75	95	+20
P2	80	100	+20
P3	60	85	+25

⁸⁰ See Appendix 4, 92.

The MMHKI pretest and posttest demonstrated that P1, P2, and P3 increased in the basic psychology of mental health. Demonstrating an understanding of mental health from developmental perspective was also achieved as a cognitive goal. All three participants correctly identified the definitions such as depression, anxiety disorders, and schizophrenia, which indicated some understanding mental health conditions. All three participants conveyed that they had a better understanding of and were better equipped to address mental health. All participants agreed the mental health was an extensive subject in which one needs to become well versed.

Overall, I found adequate demonstrable change to indicate the cognitive objective was achieved. More instructive lectures and dialogue, however, would allow for an even better understanding of mental health skillsets. More questions and assessment tools would also allow for a better analysis regarding participants' understanding of the mental health.

For the affective objective, the pastors exhibited more openness in expressing personal feelings, religious points of views, and personal values regarding mental health. To assess the accomplishment of this objective, I used reported responses as indicators of participants' ability to deal with mental health concerns. The PPFV aided greatly in assessing affective objective related to the perceptual sense of mental health. I also filled out a Teacher/Facilitator's Evaluation Form (TSEF)⁸¹ at the conclusion of each session.

As a cutoff for session attendance, I considered a 67-percent-or-more participation rate in group discussions and homework completion rate to demonstrate adequately the

⁸¹ See Appendix 8, 98.

first two affective indicators. In addition, I recommended a specific number of times pastors would incorporate mental health or its skillsets within sermons or meetings during the project. I conveyed that my intentions were for everything that transpired to flow spiritually within the context of presentation.

The following table shows the discussion participation percentages and homework completion percentages for the six sessions:

Table 2. Group Discussion and Homework Percentages

Task	Session 1	Session 2	Session 3	Session 4	Session 5	Session 6
Group Discussion	67% or more					
Homework Completion	N/A	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

During the second session, all three participants indicated they had started subtly to introduce the need for mental health awareness and skillsets to subordinate leaders. All three participants had also shared the nature of the sessions with their spouses. By sixth session, all participants shared that they had incorporated field project material consistently within conversations with church leaders. By the third session, all three participants communicated that 1 Thessalonians 5:23, regarding each person's consisting of a "spirit, soul, and body," had become an instrumental verse to help frame mental health Biblically.

I also encouraged the participants to watch a video entitled "Promoting Mental Health Equity in Black Churches." Because it was created by the National Alliance on

Mental Illness (NAMI), I felt that it would serve as an informative and relevant resource. During the third session, the three participants admitted they were fascinated by in relevancy and content of the project material. P3 stated that he also shared the video with his leaders. Three of the discussion topics the participants found essential were racial disparities in depression care, feasibility of church-based care, and community-partnered service delivery.

After I administered the MMHKI, the participants' shared about their candid responses regarding their personal mental health. The MMHKI facilitated open group discussions that aided in elevating their personal mental health awareness. I emphasized the importance of leaders not only knowing the proper resources for others but also for themselves.

The following table indicates the total PPF-PPFF-reported teachable moments for each session:

Table 3. Reported Teachable Moments

Session	Number of Teachable Moments Reported
Session 2	1
Session 3	2
Session 5	3
Session 6	3

By the sixth session, all participants had experienced teachable moments either within their personal lives, with other church leaders, or members. P1, P2, and P3 each expressed the value they found in having teachable moments. All three participants

agreed that they felt more empowered and were able to intentionally engage people on a more interpersonal level.

The skill related objective was for pastors to show improvement communicating mental health skillsets through dialogue and sermonic discourse. The scope of this project did not allow for the assessment of subordinate church leaders or members. I, therefore, relied more on expressed intent on the PPEF as opposed to direct measurement of the criteria. Participants could indicate agree, undecided, or disagree with respect to skill-related statements of intent. On the PPEF, all participants agreed that they had become more confident addressing and conversing regarding mental health within their church leaders. These expressed indicators support the intent to use the skills learned in the sessions with their ministries.

Pastors openly expressed their personal feelings and values within the group and with their ministries. All three participants shared that they had no specific mental health resources or reference material, prior to the project. Near the completion of the project, P3 shared his idea of incorporating psychological profile of the main characters, during the introduction of future sermons. P1 and P2 agreed that in many instances the psychological makeup of Biblical characters are often overlooked or dealt with inadequately.

P1, P2, and P3 indicated that over the course of six sessions that they began to use mental health and psychological terminology. In addition, P3 indicated that he planned to administer a MMHKI to all of his church leaders. P1, P2, and P3 emphasized that they felt all of the information addressed within the MMHKI should be shared with everyone.

All participants agreed that one of the benefits of the project was that they were now better equipped to identify common mental health issues.

Table 4. Participants' Skill-Related Intentions

Capability to Use in Ministry	P1	P2	P3
Active Listening	Agree	Agree	Agree
Proper Psychological/Mental Health Terminologies	Agree	Agree	Agree
Problem Solving for Mental Health Issues	Agree	Agree	Agree
Wording and Body Language	Agree	Agree	Agree

During all sessions participants conveyed that they understood the importance of body language and intonations as vital forms of communication.

Analysis and Evaluation of Personal Data

I gauged the analysis of my personal growth based primarily based upon my passion to address a very uncomfortable but well-needed topic. Ultimately, my goal was to challenge myself to grow in and breath of knowledge so I could help others. I have elected to use minimal footnotes in this section.

The research regarding the project has opened my eyes even more to humanity of everyone. Everyone matters. The million-dollar question is not if we become mentally wounded, but when. If a person lives long enough, some sort of trauma is evitable. Throughout this entire doctoral program, I have read countless books and scholarly articles regarding various cultures and their religious beliefs. Ultimately, for this project,

my goal was to narrow my focus on one specific culture, one specific issue, and to research its impact. The overall intent was not to favor any given culture but to address mental health within African American churches and communities, systems, hierarchies, and gatekeepers could be excluded.

Over the past two years, I have read countless examples of how the Gospel has transformed lives, communities, and cultures; yet many, if not most, African American churches fail to communicate the totality of the Gospel. In other words, there is a lack of imperativeness in effectively communicating that God cares about every facet of our being.

There has been a traditional consensus within the majority of African American cultures to embrace life as-is. This misperception lays a foundation for ineffective prayers, leaves little to no room to grow or seek help, when needed. For me, throughout this project the underlying current has been that God cares for each person from three distinctive points of view.

From 1 Thessalonians 5:23, it is conveyed that God sees each of us as a spirit, body, and soul. Because the soul is comprised of the mind, the will and the emotions of a person, it matters. Because it matters, it is essential to living a wholesome and holy life, in the sight of God. Throughout the New Testament there are numerous examples of Jesus healing sick and broken people.

Although God can and does answer prayer, praying without any actions creates complacency. On the other hand, pastors that fosters this type of environment complicit. I believe that the call to action within African American churches to reexamine Scripture with an open mind from a post-enslaved perspective. Unlike, the Israelites of the Exodus,

the challenge for African Americans have been to remain in the same land where their forefathers were enslaved.

As a result, African American churches must address the psychological impact of a former racially-caste system and its residual-effects guised in intersectionality within their communities. This can only be achieved through communicating the pure unadulterated word of God. Pray is just a starting point; but in order for a culture to heal three-dimensionally, counseling is sometimes needed. In many instances, a person's self-image can become an obstacle.

One of the earliest Biblical examples of this can be found in Exodus 4:10. When called by God to go and speak to Pharaoh, Moses exclaimed that he was not eloquent in speech. On the contrary, in Luke 7:22, Luke wrote this Moses was educated and eloquent in speech. From a psychological premise, Moses, an Israelite raised by Pharaoh's daughter, could have easily struggled with his cultural identity. In a nutshell, he may have had a problem with his self-image regarding his ability to speak eloquently.

Before I consider several examples within the New Testament, it would be remiss of me not to address the Old Testament. Since most African Americans are descendants of the Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade, a Biblical approach to recovery should be considered. As with the Israelites after being enslaved in Egypt, African Americans freedom was a deliberate act of God. It was not coincidental.

Prior to exploring mental health from a cultural and Biblical perspective, I held a more one-size-fits-all point of view. Although I am quite familiar some of the residual trauma from the African American Experience and the Bible, I had never delved deeply into the potential connections or remedies. If we truly are the sum of our experiences and

God is author of our faith, our co-authoring requires us to work. Depending upon the circumstances, our work as Christians is not exclusive to church but to seek out systems that can aid in the healing process.

According to 2 Timothy 2:27, “For God hath not given us the spirit of fear; but of power, and of love, and of a sound mind.” As a standalone verse, this speaks volumes. When fear, which is often a result of traumatic experiences, exists in our day-to-day lives it is not God sent. Because He is a God of love, He desires the best for his children. When fear is allowed to grow to excess, it will eventually lead to feelings of victimization and powerlessness. Fear and powerlessness were never designed to be a part of a Christians testimony. Because we are human, there are seasons when our faith will be challenged; but fear and a lack of power should never be our resolve. As further evidence in this verse, ultimately, God’s intent is for us to have a sound mind. In a nutshell, His intent is for those created in His image to be able to recover from a blow.

Before this epiphany, I held a more pragmatic view of God and mental health. Although I had always been pro-Christian counseling, other common mental health issues such as post-traumatic stress disorder, schizophrenia, or bipolar disorder went unnoticed or unaddressed. This research forced me to deal with the elephant in the living room. I believe the more Christians know about any particular subject, the more fervent and specific our prayers become.

A paradigm in the early church often associated suffering as an indicator of piety and holiness. Although Jesus healed those who suffered and were sick, including those with mental health issues, after His ascension, many in the Church developed a misconception regarding suffering. As a consequence, crucial and detrimental mental

health issues were left unaddressed. Even now, I have encountered Christians who feel inhibited regarding talking about mental health concerns. Some Christians still believe solely in Jesus and prayer for answers for everything. Because of an misinformed outdated understanding of the Bible and a lack of understanding mental health skillsets, numerous maladies still plague many churches. For instance, victims of sexual trauma or domestic violence are less likely report instances and seek guidance within their churches or professional help. This often comes from a distorted view of themselves and a lack of understanding God's purpose for their lives.

A few years ago, while attending Southeastern Baptist Theological Seminary, I took seven courses and earned a Certificate in Biblical Counseling. Of the seven courses, the one that resonated with me the most was Counseling Individuals with Problematic Emotions. The specifics of that course gave me a deeper understanding of establishing Biblical strategies to navigate depression, grief, anger, trauma, and other emotional challenges. Overall, the entire program was an eye-opening experience that made me see myself and others in a different light. So much of who we are and have the potential to become is linked to our experiences and lessons learned. Regardless of the trauma, I encourage Christians to also use Scripture as a resource for answers.

In that addressing the topic of mental health in predominately African American religious settings could be ultrasensitive, I was sensitive and considerate in my approach towards the subject. To safeguard my approach and appeal to all learning, I used the Bible as my first and primary reference. I believed that if I could convincingly convey God's concern with mental health, the theoretical resources would be seriously considered.

Because I am an extraverted personality type, I enjoy sharing, teaching, and coaching. More specifically, according to how A. J. Drenth categorizes personalities in *The 16 Personality Types: Profiles, Theory, & Type Development*, I am considered an ENFJ type. Using a concept of the Briggs-Myers Type Indicator (BTMI), based upon Carl Jung's theory of psychological types, Drenth's book stated:

While 'working a crowd' or charming an audience is undoubtedly invigorating for ENFJs, their desire to engage with people goes beyond mere superficials. Their auxiliary function, Introverted Intuition (Ni), adds a degree of depth that is less apparent in their ESFJ counterparts. Like INFJs, ENFJs see it as their job to help others live more authentically, ethically, and healthily. Utilizing their insight into people, they can be quite effective at diagnosing problems and formulating solutions that spawn personal growth. And because ENFJs are the most convincing (even if a bit forceful) of all the personality types, others often respond well to their counsel.⁸²

I believed understanding my personality type served as an invaluable tool when attempting to connect with the participants. An advantage of this personality type is having an innate desire to see others win. I understood that the perceiving functions of the participants would be either introverted sensing, extraverted sensing, introverted intuition, or extraverted intuition.

I also found Stephen E. Brookfield's concepts and ideas in *The Skillful Teacher on Technique, Trust, and Responsiveness in the Classroom*⁸³, an invaluable resource. He reinforced the imperative for teachers and facilitators to utilize a Critical Incident Questionnaires (CIQ) to access dynamics or tensions that are either conducive to learning or constructing a barrier. Although all participants had the same vocation, I remained

⁸² Andrew J Drenth, *The 16 Personality Types : Profiles, Theory, & Type Development* (United States): Inquire Books, 2017).

⁸³ Stephen D Brookfield, *The Skillful Teacher* (John Wiley & Sons, 2009).

aware that their learning styles would vary. I utilized a lesson plan that would benefit all learning styles.

The National Alliance on Mental Illness (NAMI) provided a plethora of information and fully developed lesson plans. In addition, they also provided relevant information regarding barriers to mental health care, cultural stigmas, and how to seek out competent mental health resources. Because NAMI addressed both mental and physical health care, including videos, and links to other agencies, I consider them a treasure-trove for this topic.

Because I am an extravert and dominant personality, I was always mindful to exercise constraint and show tolerance for any differing opinions held by participants. For this group, since all participants were pastors, the Bible remained the common denominator. P1 stated on a PPEF that the questions asked were well formulated, substantive, and relative and reflective of my uniquely brilliant perspective and profundity towards producing a needed body of work.

The following table presents several PPEF assessments related to my facilitating sessions:

Table 5. Evaluation of Facilitator

Evaluated Perception	P1	P2	P3
Demonstrated Tolerance	Agree	Agree	Agree
Well Prepared	Agree	Agree	Agree
Led Interesting Discussions	Agree	Agree	Agree
Embarrassed as a Participant	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree

I believe the table data and previously noted comments by the participants are indicative of the welcoming environment that was fostered. These indicators also show that I did not impose my influence or values on the participants. Each participant evaluated my performance as a facilitator without influence, coercion, or prejudice.

In this section, I have endeavored to clarify my personal theological and theoretical positions regarding the Bible and mental health skillsets. Resources were provided to substantiate all mental health concepts, therapies, or practices. I have also demonstrated the ability to teach a varied group of pastors. I met both the cognitive and skill-related goals for this project.

Analysis and Evaluation of Project Data

In this section, I identified some of the general insights regarding this project. I further made suggested improvements for the project. I then presented the Project Assessment Interview Form (PAIF)⁸⁴ results and finally offered several future uses for the project.

Initially, I considered five to seven participants for the project. After a more careful consideration of the time required and the time-consuming commitment for participants, I chose to select three. Of the three participants selected, all were eager to commit and adjusted their schedules accordingly for the entirety of the project. Although, one participant experienced a death in his family, it did not impact the momentum of the project, to include meetings and assignments.

⁸⁴ See Appendix 11, 102.

I decided that the best way to approach this project would be primarily from qualitative research with elements of quantitative data in the form of a field research project. As the project progressed, it became even more obvious to the participants and to me of its necessity and timeliness. Throughout each session, the participants grew in comfortableness and comradery.

To yield the best possible results from this project, its ministerial value was kept at the forefront. I realized that the conclusion of this project would only serve as the beginning of a part of ministry that has gone overlooked or unaddressed. I came to resolve of knowing the strongest indicate of likely demonstrable change as a result of this project would be the serious and continuous implementation and application of mental health skillsets. This project was designed to impact the pulpits and the pews. The challenge for the participants was to learn, then do. Throughout the project, I consistently reemphasized an original idiom, “Mental health begins with me.” With that being said, my primary focus was not only for the participants to garner information and resources for their churches but mostly for themselves first. In a nutshell, I intended for them to see the value in practicing what they were going to preach. Ultimately, my goal was for each participant to make the connection between God and His desire for man to be able to care for himself.

During six two-hour sessions, a plethora of information was always introduced. Each participant always contributed to the group discussions and given additional resources for information. All three participants agreed with statement five of the PPEF that the course was too short; however, P2 conveyed that he was also extremely eager to start implementing what he had learned. Since all participants had foreknowledge of the

purpose and timeline for the project, they approached its completion as their opportunity to begin. By the fourth session, P3 stated that he had already spoken with his church leaders about starting a mental health small group.

As a final means of evaluating the project, I asked the participants share their insights, discoveries, changes, and recommendations regarding the project. In addition, another intent of the PAIF was to allow participants to become as transparent as possible in order to capture their growth, reservations, and application.

P1 became more self-aware. P1 stated burnout had become normal and unaddressed and was disguised church work. P1 stated that he had personally grown and saw the value of delegating to develop other leaders and to protect one's mental health. P1 also stated that the project gave him more information and greater insight to help a relative with a mental health issue. P1 stated that the mental health resources were practical and extremely useful, and that each session's Bible study laid the foundation for discussion. P1 made the following recommendations for the project: (1) create a monthly online mental health forum for African American church leaders, and (2) establish mental health workshops for church leaders within our local communities.

P2 discovered the necessity for viewing mental health from the unique experience of African Americans. P2 claimed to have become more open-minded to some theoretical resources presented during the sessions. P2 also conveyed a greater and more in depth understanding of the theological aspects of mental health due to our Bible studies. P2 claimed to use more mental health terminology and has moved from only prayer to taking action for mental health concerns. As recommendations, P2 suggested the following: (1) creating a hybrid of the sessions that would last eight weeks and (2) creating workshops

within local community churches. P2 also stated that the facilitator was engaging and informed.

P3 gained greater insight about the African American Experience. P3 stated that the theoretical information and resources provided answers to a lot of mental health questions. P3 claimed he felt more comfortable talking about mental health, resources, and its Biblical perspective. P3 also conveyed the desire to continue pursuing mental health skillsets and strategies by attending future conferences and workshops designed for Christians. Overall, P3 indicated a sense of empowerment. P3 suggested the following: (1) increasing the sessions from six to eight online for pastors and ministers, (2) hosting mental health workshops at different churches and reformations to include their annual conferences, and (3) establishing a pastoral mental health support group for encouragement and accountability.

Conclusion

The following table depicts PPEF responses that are indicative of ministry change in participants' lives:

Table 6. Ministry Change Indicators

Change from Project	P1	P2	P3
Learned a Lot	Agree	Agree	Agree
More Effectively Address Mental Health Skillsets	Agree	Agree	Agree
Better Prepared to Discuss Mental Health	Agree	Agree	Agree

Change from Project	P1	P2	P3
No Effect on My Life	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Feel Better about Self	Agree	Agree	Agree
Better Christian	Agree	Agree	Agree

The overall ministry project served its stated purpose to achieve a demonstrable change in the participants lives that would also impact their ministries. The participants responses to several questions on the PPEF provided valuable insights into the project’s overall effectiveness. All participants disagreed that no change had occurred in their lives as a result of the project. Furthermore, all participants shared they felt about themselves personally and as Christians. In addition, all participants agreed that they learned a lot and were more prepared to address and discuss mental health with their church leaders and members.

Overall, the ministry project served its stated purpose of equipping African American pastors with mental health skillsets. Through this project, I have learned to perform intentional, informed, and instructional ministry. I have also shared as a mentor and Christian example for the participants in this project.

APPENDIX 1

COGNITIVE THEORY

Stage	Age	Behavior
Sensorimotor	0-2 years old	Coordination of senses with motor responses, sensory curiosity about the world. Language used for demands and cataloguing. Object permanence is developed.
Preoperational	2-7 years old	Symbolic thinking, use of proper syntax and grammar to express concepts, but complex abstract thoughts are still difficult. Conservation is developed.
Concrete Operational	7-11 years old	Concepts attached to concrete situations. Time, space, and quantity are understood and can be applied, but not as independent concepts.
Formal Operational	11 years old and older	Theoretical, hypothetical, and counterfactual thinking. Abstract logic and reasoning. Strategy and planning become possible. Concepts learned in one context can be applied to another.

Source: Jean Piagets Theory of Cognitive Development
<https://www.structural-learning.com/post/jean-piagets-theory-of-cognitive-development-and-active-classrooms>

APPENDIX 2

PSYCHODYNAMIC THEORY

Age	Conflict	Resolution or "Virtue"	Culmination in Old Age
Infancy (0-1 year)	Basic trust vs. Mistrust	Hope	Appreciation of interdependence and relatedness
Early childhood (1-3 year)	Autonomy vs. Shame	Will	Acceptance of the cycle of life, from integration to disintegration
Play Age (3-6 year)	Initiative vs. Guilt	Purpose	Humor; empathy; resilience
School Age (6-12 year)	Industry vs. Inferiority	Competence	Humility; acceptance of the course of one's life and unfulfilled hopes
Adolescence (12-19 year)	Identity vs. Confusion	Fidelity	Sense of complexity of life; merging of sensory, logical, and aesthetic perception
Early Adulthood (20-25 year)	Intimacy vs. Isolation	Love	Sense of the complexity of relationships; value of tenderness and loving freely
Adulthood (26-64 year)	Generativity vs. Stagnation	Care	Caritas, caring for others, and agape, empathy and concern
Old Age (65-death)	Integrity vs. Despair	Wisdom	Existential identity: a sense of integrity strong enough to withstand physical disintegration

Source: Erickson's Stage Theory in its Final Version

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APPENDIX 3

BEHAVIORAL THEORY

Age	Moral Level	Description
Young children- usually prior to age 9	Preconventional Morality	<p>Stage 1: Focus is on self-interest and punishment is avoided. The man should steal the drug, as he may get caught and go to jail.</p> <p>Stage 2: Rewards are sought. A person at this level will argue that the man should steal the drug because he does not want to lose his wife who takes care of him</p>
Older children, adolescents, and most adults	Conventional Morality	<p>Stage 3: Focus is on how situational outcomes impact others and wanting to please and be accepted. The man should steal the drug because that is what good husbands do.</p> <p>Stage 4: People make decisions based on laws or formalized rules. The man should obey the law because stealing is a crime.</p>
Rare with adolescents and few adults	Postconventional Morality	<p>Stage 6: Moral behavior is based on self-chosen ethical principles. The man should steal the drug because life is more important than property.</p>
	Transcendental Morality, or Morality of Cosmic Origin	<p>Stage 7: Consists of religion with moral reasoning.</p>

Source: Kohlberg's Stages of Moral Development
<https://courses.lumenlearning.com/suny-lifespandevelopment/chapter/kohlbergs-stages-of-moral-development/>

APPENDIX 4

SELECTION OF THE MENTAL HEALTH SERIES

I reviewed the following two mental health-oriented publications to aid in the pastors understanding mental health within their churches: (1) *Reading the Bible for Guidance, Comfort, and Strength During Stressful Life Events*, published by Nursing Research: Advancing the Science Improving Patient Care and (2) *When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing*, published by W Publishing Group, An Imprint of Thomas Nelson.

My criteria for selecting which one to choose as a resource for the project were as follows: (1) the content should be Christian and Biblically-based; (2) the information within the series should contain credible and relevant information to mental health; (3) the information should be comprehensive and not too complexed; and (4) the mental health material should be presented in a manner that encourage pastoral acceptance.

I reviewed the content of both and evaluated them based on my stated criteria. I selected content from the book *When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing*.

After selected this series, I consulted with three pastors (non-participants) for their assessment, opinions, and evaluation of the book's content. After a week of review, all three pastors concurred with its relevancy and content. My primary goal was to ensure that it did not contain any errancy according to Scripture.

I then tested elements gleaned from *When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing*, during two Christian premarital counseling sessions. The couple that I counseled had both suffered from

traumatic events, prior to dating. One person had been the victim of infidelity and struggled with trust, whereas the other person struggled with low self-esteem.

While counseling the couple, I concluded that *When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing* would be beneficial for addressing mental health and emotions from a spiritual and Biblical context. I was thoroughly impressed with the contents of this book. The book also has a workbook, but unfortunately, it is no longer available for order.

When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing, printed in 2022, contained a lot of relevant information that I often used within my six sessions. The authors were intentional to frame its topics from a Biblical perspective. The topics addressed were as follows: (1) Jesus and a Therapist, (2) Add Hope to Your Faith, (3) Become Your Best Self, (4) Own it, Then Change It, (5) Face Your Fear Factor, (6) Understand the Problems and the Purposes of Anger, (7) Find Grace for Guilt and Shame, (8) Feel Your Pain to Heal, (9) Recognize Your Toxic People, (10) Release Your toxic People and Refocus Your Life, (11) Experience Forgiveness by Letting Go, (12) Protect Your Peace, then Live in it, (13) the Seven Keys to Healthy Relationships, (14) Grow Through Grief and Loss, (15) Unleash Your Inner Power, and (16) Change Everything with Gratitude.

This book proved itself to be invaluable in a plethora of ways. Each chapter used several Scriptures to exemplify how we as Christians should choose to respond and emote, during difficult times.

APPENDIX 5

PARTICIPANT'S PERIODIC FEEDBACK FORM

Name _____ Date _____

1. Reading Assignment:

- (1) Did you complete the assignment? Y__N__N/A__
- (2) Did you find it helpful? Y__N__N/A__
- (3) Did you read any additional sources on the Same subject matter? Y__N__N/A__

2. Written Assignment:

- (1) Did you complete the assignment? Y__N__N/A__
- (2) Did you find it helpful? Y__N__N/A__

3. Teachable Moments:

- (1) Did any teachable moments occur since the last report? Y__N__N/A__
- (2) Did you use subject matter learned in this Program during the teachable moment? Y__N__N/A__
- (3) If a teachable moment occurred, briefly describe the situation, your responses, and any subject matter learned during this program which you used:

4. Evaluation:

- (1) At this point in the program, are you being helped in your understanding of mental health? Y__N__N/A__
- (2) Is the teacher being clear in his/her presentation of the subject matter? Y__N__N/A__
- (3) Do you have any suggestions for improving the program? Y__N__N/A__

5. Any additional comments:

APPENDIX 6

PARTICIPANT’S PERSONAL GOALS FORM

Note: This form is to be completed by all participants at the conclusion of the six seminar sessions. It is to be placed in the participant’s personal file and used as an evaluation instrument.

Name _____ Date _____

(Key: A=agree; U=undecided; D=disagree—Circle One)

A U D 1. Every church needs to develop definite plans for teaching mental health skillsets.

A U D 2. The primary responsibility for promoting mental health within churches are pastors.

A U D 3. Mental Health skillsets is primarily the sharing of facts.

A U D 4. Churches have potential theological resources available for teaching mental health.

A U D 5. The preaching/teaching content should periodically address mental health.

6. Outline your plans for teaching mental health in your ministry:

A. Pastoral Preparation _____

B. Church Leaders Preparations _____

C. Action Plan (Step-by-step procedures to put the plan into operation) _____

7. List resources you plan to utilize: _____

8. Would you seek extra help from mental health professionals if the need arise?

Y__N__ Why or why not? _____

APPENDIX 7

MODIFIED MENTAL HEALTH KNOWLEDGE INVENTORY

Section I

Directions: In this section you may indicate knowledgeability by correctly regarding the following mental health disorder terminologies.

1. Anxiety Disorders	3. Bipolar Disorder	5. Eating Disorder	7. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder	9. Schizophrenia
2. Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)	4. Depression	6. Obsessive-compulsive Disorder (OCD)	8. Psychosis	10. Dissociative Disorder

5 _____ are characterized by the intentional changing of food consumption to the point where physical health or social behaviors are affected.

10 _____, which are frequently associated with trauma, disrupt every area of psychological functioning: consciousness, memory, identity, emotion, motor control and behavior.

6 _____ involves persistent, intrusive thoughts (obsessions) and repetitive behaviors that a person feels driven to perform (compulsions) in response to those thoughts.

9 _____ interferes with a person's ability to think clearly, manage emotions, make decisions and relate to others. It also causes people to lose touch with reality, often in the form of hallucinations and delusions.

8 _____ is characterized as disruptions to a person's thoughts and perceptions that make it difficult for them to recognize what is real and what isn't.

1 Everyone can experience _____, but when symptoms are overwhelming and constant — often impacting everyday living — it may be an anxiety disorder.

7 _____ involves a set of physiological and psychological responses. It can occur in people who have experienced or witnessed a traumatic event such as a natural disaster, a serious accident, a terrorist act, rape, war/combat or something similar.

4 _____ involves recurrent, severe periods of clear-cut changes in mood, thought processes and motivation lasting for a minimum of two weeks. Changes in thought processes typically include negative thoughts and hopelessness. Depression also involves affects sleep/energy, appetite or weight.

2 _____ is a developmental disorder defined by inattention (trouble staying on task, listening); disorganization (losing materials); and hyperactivity-impulsivity (fidgeting, difficulty staying seated or waiting).

3 _____ causes dramatic shifts in a person's mood, energy and ability to think clearly. Individuals with this disorder experience extreme high and low moods, known as mania and depression. Some people can be symptom-free for many years between episodes.

Section II

Directions: In this section you may identify the correct response. Within the brackets are the correct answers from a multiple choices per question online presentation.

1. Poor mental health increases the risk for long-lasting (chronic) physical conditions all the above.
2. Mental illnesses are very common.

3. Suicide is the [2nd] leading cause of death among people ages 10 to 24 in the United States.
4. Mental illness [can be treated.]
5. Mental health is [an important part of overall health.]
6. If you know someone with poor mental health, you can help by [all the above.]
7. People with mental illness are violent. [False]
8. Half of mental illnesses occur before a person turns [14] years old.
9. Serious mental illness costs America how much in lost earnings per year? [193.2] billion in lost earnings per year.
10. Mental illness is caused by [several factors including traumatic events, biological and family history, stress, heart disease, and cancer.]

Section III

Directions: In the section identify and fill in the blank answer with the correct type of disorder, risk, or aid associated with mental health concerns listed within the table below.

Anosognosia	Self-harm	Psychotherapy	Sleep Disorders	Brain Stimulation Therapies
Substance Use Disorders	Mental Health Medications	Risk of Suicide	Autism	Smoking

1. Substance use disorders — the repeated misuse of alcohol and/or drugs — often occur simultaneously in individuals with mental illness, usually to cope with overwhelming symptoms.
2. Self-harm is usually a sign that a person is having a tough time coping with their emotions. It’s frequently “used” as a coping mechanism for unmanageable mental illness symptoms.
3. Anosognosia is when someone is unaware of their own mental illness or when they can’t perceive their symptoms accurately.
4. Suicidal thoughts often accompany mental illness. Not taking these kinds of thoughts seriously can have devastating outcomes. Suicide can be prevented.
5. Autism is a complex developmental disorder that can cause problems with thinking, feeling, language and the ability to relate to others. Many individuals with autism also live with mental illness like anxiety or depression.
6. Living with a mental illness can be difficult, and some people may turn to smoking as a way to cope with symptoms or handle stressful life events.
7. Anxiety, depression and other mental health conditions are often accompanied by sleep disorders that should also be addressed in treatment.
8. Some people find mental health medications to be an important part of their treatment plan. Understanding their risks and benefits can help you make the right choice.
9. Psychotherapy, also known as “talk therapy,” is when a person speaks with a trained therapist in a safe and confidential environment to explore and understand feelings and behaviors and gain coping skills.
10. When treatments such as medication and therapy aren’t able to relieve the symptoms of depression or another mental health condition, brain stimulation therapies can be an option.

APPENDIX 8

TEACHER/FACILATATOR'S EVALUATION FORM

Class or group:_____ Date_____

1. Attendance Report: (Number present and names of absentees if possible): _____

2. Evaluation of participants' group dynamics:
- Excellent (75% or more joined in discussions)
 - Good (50% or more joined in joined in the discussions)
 - Fair (25% or more joined in discussions)
 - Poor (Less than 25% joined in discussions)

3. Evaluation of participants' preparation for the seminars:
- Excellent (75% completed homework)
 - Good (50% completed homework)
 - Fair (25% completed homework)
 - Poor (Less than 25% completed homework)

4. Facilitator's overall sense of satisfaction with the session:
- Excellent
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor

5. Additional Comments: _____

6. Observer's Feedback if applicable: _____

APPENDIX 9

PARTICIPANT'S PROJECT EVALUATION FORM

Participant's name or number: _____

(Key: A=agree; U=undecided; D=disagree-Circle one)

- A U D 1. This project has been helpful to me.
- A U D 2. I enjoyed the reading materials for this project.
- A U D 3. The reading material was too graphic in its discussion of mental health and/or race.
- A U D 4. The length of the project was too long.
- A U D 5. The length of the project was too short.
- A U D 6. The teacher was well prepared for each session.
- A U D 7. I will use the active-listening skills learned in this course with others.
- A U D 8. The group discussions were interesting.
- A U D 9. The information on the understanding of mental health was a waste of time.
- A U D 10. I was embarrassed throughout the sessions.
- A U D 11. I shared what I learned with my church leaders.
- A U D 12. The project attempted to cover too much material.
- A U D 13. Some of the things discussed were difficult to understand.
- A U D 14. I better understand and can do mental health education as a result of this course.
- A U D 15. I was surprised to discover some of my friends had some of the same problems I have.
- A U D 16. I am a better Christian because of this project.
- A U D 17. The Bible was over-emphasized during the sessions.
- A U D 18. It is best to use proper mental health terminology in formal discussions.
- A U D 19. I believe that mental health should not be a taboo topic.
- A U D 20. I feel better about myself after taking this course.
- A U D 21. My lifestyle has not been affected after taking this course.
- A U D 22. I learned a lot of things I did not know because of this course.
- A U D 23. I can now use teachable moments to share mental health skillsets with my family and church leaders.
- A U D 24. The test were hard to understand
- A U D 25. The written assignments were unnecessary.
- A U D 26. As a result of this course, I plan to use more mental health terminology when conversing on the topic.
- A U D 27. I have some mental health problems that I need to talk with someone about.

Continued on the next page.

Participant's name and number: _____

A U D 28. The course needs more discussion and less paperwork.

A U D 29. I can now use more effective communication skills in my ministry as a result of taking this course.

A U D 30. Up to this point in my life, I knew very little about mental health.

A U D 31. The mental health skillsets I learned in this course will help me address mental health issues within my family and ministry.

A U D 32. Mental Health challenges should be considered as a normal part of life.

A U D 33. I am glad God created us differently.

A U D 34. The facilitator demonstrated a spirit of tolerance of various ideas during the course.

A U D 35. I do not believe that people are crazy.

A U D 36. People with mental health issues should not be stigmatized.

A U D 37. Our online connectivity was consistent.

A U D 38. This course will help me more effectively address mental health within my ministry.

A U D 39. I am better prepared to discuss mental health with others as a result of taking this course.

A U D 40. I recommend this course to other persons.

Other comments: (If a comment refers to a specific question please list the question number prior to the comment: _____

APPENDIX 10

PARTICIPANT'S ENROLLMENT AND PERSONAL HISTORY FORM

Name _____ Month- Year of birth _____
Address _____

Phone: Work _____ Home _____

E-mail Address (if available): _____

Children: (Complete name/Male or Female/Month- Year of birth) _____

Spiritual Status:

Christian Y__ N__ Church Member Y__ Where _____ N__

Areas where you are involved in the church? _____

Briefly indicate any formal mental health training you have participated in _____

Why do you want to be a part of this mental health training program? _____

Indicate any reservations or questions you might have if you were selected to participate in this program _____

Printed below is a written agreement of participation. Please read it carefully and sign below if you agree to fully participate in this program of mental health education training.

I agree to participate faithfully in the mental health skillset training program offered online, hosted in Clarksville, Tennessee. I further agree to attend all six sessions of the training unless providentially hindered. I also pledge myself to read and complete assigned materials and to complete the various assessment forms are required during the program. In addition, I commit myself seriously to pray that God would bring spiritual growth in my life and in my ministry during this opportunity for personal growth.

Date _____

Signed _____

APPENDIX 11

PROJECT ASSESSMENT INTERVIEW FORM

Participant's Name _____ Date _____

1. DISCOVERIES:

- a. While taking the course, did you discover anything about yourself? If so, what?

- b. Did you discover anything about others? If so, what?

2. CHANGES:

- a. As a result of the course, have there been any changes in your feelings or attitudes? If so, what?

- b. Have there been any changes in your approach towards people with mental health concerns?

- c. Have there been any changes in your approaches towards pastoring in general and with respect to mental health within your church or community?

3. BENEFITS:

- a. What were the greatest benefits of this course to you?

- b. Was it worth the time and effort?

- c. What did you enjoy most about the course?

Participant's Name _____

d. What were some of the least helpful things to you?

4. RECOMMENDATIONS:

a. Would you recommend that others in the church participate in training similar to this?

b. What things do you think could be done to improve the training course?

c. Was the course too long and drawn out? Or was it too short?

d. Was there too much content material given in the course? Or was there too little?

e. Was there too much outside reading assignments? Or was there too little?

f. Was there too much homework? Or was there too little?

g. Did you consult other sources regarding mental health beyond the basic course materials? If so, what?

h. The facilitator was effective in what ways? The facilitator was ineffective or needs improvement in what ways?

APPENDIX 12

PERSONAL LESSON PLANS

These lesson plans represent the materials covered in each of the six sessions. Because the sessions were taught in an online format, I utilized a combination of Power Point slides and screen sharing. I selected certain materials in order to have a variety of information and to facilitate different learning styles.

The letters “FMT” designates the use of Evans and Kaiser’s, *When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing* as the primary source for that section’s information and bullets for slides. The number following the dash indicates the respective page number of the material. The additional letters, titles, and numbers following page numbers for Evans and Kaiser’s lesson plans indicate the location of the material within the lesson plan. The letter “P” indicates materials used from this project as the primary source for that section’s information and bullets for slides.

1. Introduction:

A. Topic and Activities for the First Hour:

1. FMT-13 Course Goal, Useful Tools
2. FMT-13 Assumptions
3. P-9 Theological Rationale
4. P-31 Theoretical Presupposition
5. P-55 Objectives
6. P-47 Participants Objects
7. P-56 Personal Objectives
8. Overview of Project Session Format
9. Summary of Project and Assessment

10. *When Faith Meets Therapy: Find Hope and a Practical Path to Emotional, Spiritual, and Relational Healing*, published by W Publishing Group, An Imprint of Thomas Nelson.

B. Topics and Activities for the Second Hour:

1. Participant Enrollment and Covenanting
2. MMHKI Pretest Administration
3. Questions and Answers

II. Exploring and Understanding Mental Health

- A. PPF (10 minutes)
- B. FMT-14 I. Introduction, C. Program Rules and D. Covenanting (15 minutes)
- C. FMT-14 II. Warm-Up Activities, B. Expectations (20 minutes)
- D. FMT-14 III. A. Bible Study – Body, Spirit, and Soul (30 minutes)
- E. FMT-14 IV. Introduction to Mental Health, Misconceptions (20 minutes)
- F. FMT-15 V. Personal Mental Health, B. Taking Time for Me (20 minutes)
- G. Homework and Handouts: A. Topical Discussion (15 minutes)

III. Mental Health Disorders

- A. PPF (20 minutes)
- B. FMT-15 I. Introduction, A. Bible Study, Be Anxious for Nothing (30 minutes)
- C. FMT-17 II. Traumatic Experiences (30 minutes)
- D. MMHKI and Homework Review (30 minutes)
- E. Homework Assignment and Handouts (10 minutes)

IV. Exploring Intersectionality

- A. PPF, Questions, and Review (15 minutes)
- B. P-35 I. Understanding Race, Gender, and Intersectionality (45 minutes)
- C. FMT-29 II. Facing Fear (20 minutes)
- D. FMT-29 II. A. Bible Study – The Woman at the Well (30 minutes)
- E. Homework Assignments and Handouts (10 minutes)

V. Developing Coping Skills

- A. PPF, Questions, and Review (15 minutes)
- B. FMT-36 I. Introduction, A. Bible Study, Resiliency in Tough Times (30 minutes)
- C. From Handouts: Review additional Mental Health Terminologies (40 minutes)
- D. Homework Assignments Review and Topical Discussion (30 minutes)

II. Employing Listening Skills

- A. PFFF, Questions, and Review (15 minutes)
- B. From Handouts: Introduction & Using Active Listening Skills (30 minutes)
- C. Bible Study – Being Quick to Listen (30 minutes)
- D. MMHKI Posttest (20 minutes)
- E. Review of Handouts, Homework and the Five Previous Sessions (25 minutes)

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